

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957781.

active **c**ommunities & **e**nergy
prosumers for the energy **t**ransition

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER 957781

WP6 - ACCEPT solution integration, pre-validation, roll-out

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

Responsible organisation	CIRCE
Contributing organisation(s)	Hypertech, QUE, Witside, CERTH
Due date of Deliverable	31/05/2023
Actual date of submission	30/06/2023
Type of deliverable	Demonstrator
Dissemination level	Public

Disclaimer: ACCEPT is a project co-funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 - Call: H2020-SC3-2018-2020 EC-3 Consumer engagement and demand response Programme under Grant Agreement No. 957781. The information and views set out in this publication are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Communities. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use, which may be made, of the information contained therein.

© Copyright in this document remains vested with the ACCEPT Partners

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

Authors

Name	Organisation	e-mail	Role
Aitor Alcrudo	CIRCE	aalcrudo@fcirce.es	Main Author
Alberto Mur	CIRCE	amur@fcirce.es	Author
Ismiini Dimitriadou	Hypertech	i.dimitriadou@hypertech.gr	Contributor
Christina Malapani	Hypertech	c.malapani@hypertech.gr	Contributor
Kosmas Petridis	Hypertech	k.petridis@hypertech.gr	Contributor
Maria Diamantaki	CERTH	mardiama@iti.gr	Contributor
Ioannis Koskinas	CERTH	jkosk@iti.gr	Contributor
Paschalis Gkaidatzis	CERTH	pgkaidat@iti.gr	Contributor
Konstantina Thomou	CERTH	kontho@iti.gr	Contributor
Panagiotis Lois	CERTH	panalois@iti.gr	Contributor
Dimosthenis Ioannidis	CERTH	djoannid@iti.gr	Contributor
Panagiotis Moraitis	QUE	p.moratis@que-tech.com	Contributor
Kakavoulis Stefanos-Dimitris	QUE	s.kakavoulis@que-tech.com	Contributor
Rapatsouela Theano	QUE	t.rapoutsela@que-tech.com	Contributor

Reviewers

Name	Organisation	e-mail
Panagiotis Moraitis	QUE	
Nicolas Stathopoulos	Hypertech	

Deliverable is

Fully Accepted

Accepted with minor revisions

Rejected unless modified as suggested

Fully Rejected

Version history

Version	Date	Comments
0.1	03.04.23	First shared version

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

0.2	15.05.23	Second shared version
0.3	01.06.23	Contributions by CERTH
0.4	14.06.23	Contributions by Hypertech
0.5	19.06.23	Version for review and rest of contributions
0.6	23.06.23	Version after partial review
0.7	25.06.23	Final review
1.0	27.06.23	Delivered version

Project Consortium

Austria
 • European Center for Renewable Energy Güssing GmbH

Cyprus
 • Witside International Markets LTD

Greece
 • Hypertech (Project Coordinator)
 • Εθνικό Κέντρο Έρευνας και Τεχνολογικής Ανάπτυξης
 • Mytilinaios Anonimi Etaireia
 • QUE Technologies Kefalaiouchiki Etaireia

Netherlands
 • Bedrijfsbureau Energie Samen BV
 • Energie Samen Rivierenland

Norway
 • Smart Innovation Norway

Spain
 • My Energia Oner SL
 • La Solar Energia Sociedad Cooperativa
 • Fundacion Undacion Circe Centre De Investigacion de Recursos Y Consumos Energeticos

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 959781.

List of figures

Figure 1 Dispatch of P2P energy price from the Shadow Administrator to the P2P Exchange Platform	36
Figure 2. Registering a Smart Contract on the P2P Exchange Platform.	36
Figure 3 Log files UC7	47

List of tables

Table 1 Scenario S01 Data Monitoring.....	12
Table 2 Scenario S02 Profile mechanism	12
Table 3 Scenario S03 Data visualization (Profile).....	12
Table 4 Scenario S04 request for visualization (data)	12
Table 5 Scenario S01 Self-Consumption Maximization.....	13
Table 6 Scenario S01 Building flexibility optimization	14
Table 7 Scenario S02 Building cost optimization.....	14
Table 8 Scenario S03 Comfort as a service	14
Table 9 Scenario S01 Regular Operation	15
Table 10 Scenario S01 Regular Operation.....	16
Table 11 Scenario S02 EV charging profile.....	16
Table 12 UC7 Community-level P2P flexibility/energy exchange.....	16
Table 13 Scenario S01 Receive DR request.....	17
Table 14 Scenario S01 Implicit DR.....	18
Table 15 UC12 Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation for a cost-efficient district-level DER management	19
Table 16 UC13 Increase self-consumption at community level.....	19
Table 17 BILM outbound messages	22
Table 18 BILM test status	22
Table 19 DILM outbound messages	23
Table 20 DILM test status.....	24
Table 21 DAM outbound messages	24
Table 22 DAM test status.....	26
Table 23 ODFM outbound messages	26
Table 24 ODFM test status.....	27
Table 25 CDT test status	27
Table 26 C-APP outbound messages	28
Table 27 C-APP inbound messages	28
Table 28 C-APP test status.....	28
Table 29 BILM Communication Tests	29
Table 30 AT inbound messages	31
Table 31 AT outbound messages.....	31
Table 32 AT test status.....	31
Table 33 RTs outbound messages	31
Table 34 RTs test status	32
Table 35 ASE outbound messages	32
Table 36 ASE test status.....	34
Table 37 DILM outbound messages	35
Table 38 H-ECTs outbound messages	37

Suggested Actions

Reviewer 1

The next actions should be implemented for the deliverable to be accepted

1.

2.

The next actions may be implemented for deliverable improvement

3.

4.

Formatting issues

5.

Further suggestions/comments/recommendations

Table of Content

Authors	2
Project Consortium	3
List of figures	4
List of tables	5
Suggested Actions	6
Executive summary	10
1. Introduction	11
2. Functional testing by use case	11
2.1. <i>UC1 Monitoring and Visualization of Metering & Sensor Energy Data in community buildings.</i>	11
2.2. <i>UC2 Building self-consumption employing Virtual Thermal Energy Storage optimization.</i>	13
2.3. <i>UC3 Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting and optimization taking into account comfort boundaries, activity patterns and possible requirements.</i>	13
2.4. <i>UC4 Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation and analysis in community level.</i>	15
2.5. <i>UC5 Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management for community self-balancing.</i>	15
2.6. <i>UC6 Day-ahead smart charging flexibility via EV usage pattern profiling and forecasting.</i>	15
2.7. <i>UC7 Community-level P2P flexibility/energy exchange based on locally produced renewable energy.</i> .	16
2.8. <i>UC8 Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes.</i>	17
2.9. <i>UC9 Participation in implicit Demand Response scheme.</i>	17
2.10. <i>UC10 Community flexibility bundling for local congestion management service.</i>	18
2.11. <i>UC11 Retailer Day-ahead optimal pricing configuration for aggregated portfolio balancing.</i>	18
2.12. <i>UC12 Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation for a cost-efficient district-level DER management.</i>	18
2.13. <i>UC13 Increase self-consumption at community level.</i>	19
2.14. <i>UC14 Active Citizen and LEC Engagement.</i>	19
3. Functional testing by business case	19
3.1. <i>Business case 1</i>	20
3.2. <i>Business case 2</i>	20
3.3. <i>Business case 3</i>	20
3.4. <i>Business case 4</i>	20
3.5. <i>Business case 5</i>	20
3.6. <i>Business case 6</i>	21
3.7. <i>Business case 7</i>	21

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

4.	Automated Integration testing	21
4.1.	<i>Building Information Management Layer (BILM)</i>	21
4.2.	<i>District Information Management Layer (DILM)</i>	23
4.3.	<i>District Asset Manager (DAM)</i>	24
4.4.	<i>On Demand Flexibility Manager (ODFM).....</i>	26
4.5.	<i>Consumer Digital Twin (CDT)</i>	27
4.6.	<i>P2P Exchange platform (P2P)</i>	27
4.7.	<i>Citizen Application (C-APP)</i>	27
4.8.	<i>Energy Community Tools</i>	29
4.9.	<i>Horizontal Energy Community Tools (H-ECTs)</i>	30
4.10.	<i>ESCo Tools (ET).....</i>	30
4.11.	<i>Aggregator Tools (AT).....</i>	31
4.12.	<i>Retailer Tools (RTs)</i>	31
4.13.	<i>ACCEPT solution emulator (ASE).....</i>	32
5.	Manual Integration testing	34
5.1.	<i>Building Information Management Layer (BILM)</i>	34
5.2.	<i>District Information Management Layer (DILM)</i>	34
5.3.	<i>District Asset Manager (DAM)</i>	35
5.4.	<i>On Demand Flexibility Manager (ODFM).....</i>	35
5.5.	<i>Consumer Digital Twin (CDT)</i>	35
5.6.	<i>P2P Exchange platform.....</i>	35
5.7.	<i>Citizen Application (C-APP)</i>	35
5.8.	<i>Horizontal Energy Community Tools (H-ECTs)</i>	37
5.9.	<i>ESCo Tools (ET).....</i>	37
5.10.	<i>Aggregator Tools (AT).....</i>	37
5.11.	<i>Retailer Tools (RTs)</i>	37
5.12.	<i>ACCEPT solution emulator (ASE).....</i>	37
6.	Integration schedule	37
7.	Conclusions and next steps	37
8.	Bibliography.....	38
9.	Annex A	38
9.1.	<i>Functional testing</i>	38
9.2.	<i>Integration testing</i>	51

Abbreviations

API	Application Program Interface
ASE	ACCEPT Solution Emulator
AT	Aggregator Tools
BILM	Building Information Management Layer
C-APP	Citizen Application
CDT	Consumer Digital Twin
DAM	District Assets Manager
DILM	District Information Management Layer
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operators
ET	ESCo Tools
H-ECTs	Horizontal Energy Community Tools
ODFM	On Demand Flexibility Manager
P2P	Peer to peer
RT	Retailer Tools
TSO	Transport System Operators

Executive summary

This report presents the work conducted in the iterative integration of the components specified in tasks T2.1 and T2.5.

Integration is the main focus of this document. More precisely two types of integration testing will be performed to check the specifications and functionality of the different components: automated integration testing and manual integration testing.

Independently of the type of the test, the different situations covered in the multiple tests have been described in different sections according to the use case and the business case (in each subsection of the latter one, a higher-level description of what must be tested is presented to the reader).

For each type of test, different subcategories corresponding to the ACCEPT system components will be found, with screenshots and other tests output located in the annexes where necessary to increase the clarity of the checks that have been designed and conducted.

It must be noticed that the components which have been included in an automatic testing pipeline won't appear as manually tested in the pertinent part of the document.

This is the second iteration of this document where more cohesive functioning of the prototype system is expected although some loose ends might still be present which will be tackled on the final integration iteration with a report due for M37.

1. Introduction

The purpose of this document is to iteratively (till the final version) integrate all software components of the ACCEPT system, namely the outputs of WP4/ WP5 and verify that they comply with the requirements and specifications set out in T2.1 and T2.5.

To define the different components to be tested we will use the information of the system architecture [1]. In the architecture document there are several components for which we have a description, a functional specification and a set of inputs and output. We will take each of the components and treat it as a self-contained element.

Integration of the components is done by exchanging messages and data between them. This requires that each component “understands” the messages it receives and can connect with the rest. Communication protocols were already listed on the architecture document so we will focus on the payload of the different messages. We will take the outputs that each component produces and check them against the input that the other components require.

The integration goal is to build an automatic testing platform that will ensure that the components meet the requirements for each one of the development cycles. We will test the components themselves and interacting with one another.

This is the second iteration of this document where more cohesive functioning of the prototype system is expected although some loose ends might still be present which will be tackled on the final integration iteration with a report due for M37.

This iteration of the integration testing in particular features the following improvements:

- Added control endpoint to the BIML infrastructure. Allowing actuation over building elements.
- BAM endpoints are externally accessible.
- DAM DH forecast
- ECT endpoints are externally accessible. Since the integrated energy community tool is finished, we have a test that tests it as a whole.
- New flexibility estimator endpoint for the retailer tools reflecting the particularities of the Greek and Spanish demos for better performance in the use cases.
- C-App is externally accessible and integration with the BIML and BAM is in the final stages.
- Energy Community platform is deployed and externally accessible.

Furthermore, BIML has been deployed on pilot sites acquiring real data from the pilots and testing is well under way on pilot premises.

Existing automated integration tests have been upgraded, when possible, in order to increase the robustness of the integration adding additional checks on the integrity of the data.

2. Functional testing by use case

The goal of these tests, as stated in the grant agreement, is to check that the functionality delivered by the different components conforms to what was defined in the use-case deliverable [2]. We have also taken into account the refinement of the use cases reflected on the second version of the ACCEPT architecture deliverable [1].

To achieve this, we will use the use cases themselves as a fulcrum of what needs to be tested. In this case it will not be possible to automate all the tests. Where automation is not feasible, we will do manual testing at specific points in time.

In the following section items to be checked will be coded according to the use case and the scenario they belong to so for example item UC1-S01-1 is the first item for the first scenario of the first use case.

2.1. UC1 Monitoring and Visualization of Metering & Sensor Energy Data in community buildings.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

This use case involves data monitoring and ingestion, user profiling and using the Citizen App to request data visualization. We will need to check the following items, as defined in the D2.1 deliverable:

Scenario S01 Data Monitoring

Data from sensors is read in the BILM and sent to the ESCo Tools and then to the ECTs from there the energy community can get both IoT data and static data.

Table 1 Scenario S01 Data Monitoring

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
Communication with sensors	UC1-S01-1	Yes
Data Ingestion	UC1-S01-2	Yes
ECTs request and gets data	UC1-S01-3	Yes
Energy community gets IoT data	UC1-S01-4	Yes
Energy community gets static data	UC1-S01-5	Yes

For the Items UC1-S01-3, UC1-S01-4 and UC1-S01-5 (as it is show in Table 1 for the three items), the ECTs send a request to the BIML for fetching IoT and building static data and the BIML sends those data as a response. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [FT-21-01].

Scenario S02 Profile mechanism

A profile of the user is created using user data (as it is show in Table 2).

Table 2 Scenario S02 Profile mechanism

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
Profile is created	UC1-S02-1	Yes

The user is able to create an account through the registration tab in C-APP, in order to be connected with the appropriate BIML infrastructure. (Tested on CERTH premises and pilot sites)

Scenario S03 Data visualization (Profile)

User profile data is shown in the C-APP (as it is show in Table 3).

Table 3 Scenario S03 Data visualization (Profile)

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
Profile Data is shown in the App	UC1-S03-1	Yes

The data profiling of citizen's measurements is displayed within the citizen application using various types of plot representations. (Tested on CERTH premises and pilot sites)

Scenario S04 request for visualization (data) (see Table 4)

Table 4 Scenario S04 request for visualization (data)

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
C-APP request data to BIML	UC1-S04-1	Yes
Data is shown in the App	UC1-S04-2	Yes
Data is from the correct assets/building	UC1-S04-3	Yes
Data is from the selected timeframe	UC1-S04-4	Yes

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

The proper application of communication between tools has been achieved in most cases, but occasionally, due to technical reasons, the data exchange does not occur as intended. For example, some users have technical issues to transmit data to BIML tool or connection issues (Tested on CERTH premises and pilot sites). This will be addressed by the technical partners CERTH and Hypertech for the last iteration of the document.

2.2. UC2 Building self-consumption employing Virtual Thermal Energy Storage optimization.

This scenario enables optimal scheduling of heating/cooling devices in the household using the inherent thermal storage capabilities of the building, with the aim of increasing self-consumption of renewable energy resources (PV)

Scenario S01 Self-Consumption Maximization

User (Prosumer) request self-consumption optimization using C-APP and receives an optimal schedule done by ODFM using the CDT. The schedule is applied by the BIML. Results of the optimization can be seen at prosumer level (timeseries comparison).

Table 5 Scenario S01 Self-Consumption Maximization

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
User request optimization (Self consumption SLA)	UC2-S01-1	Yes pending integration
Optimization performed by ODFM	UC2-S01-2	Yes pending integration
Optimal schedule is sent to BIML	UC2-S01-3	Yes
Implementation of optimal schedule by BIML	UC2-S01-4	Yes

UC2-S01-1 and UC2-S01-2 (as it is show in Table 5) manually tested by Hypertech. The automated service will be available for all commissioned ACCEPT sites at the end of June 2023 and, as such, the results of the automated tests will be included in the final version of the integration deliverable.

For UC2-S01-3 (as it is show in Table 5): An optimal schedule for the HVAC system of the open space at the Hypertech labs. The type of messages sent to the BIML for implementation of the optimal schedule, in this case for switching on/off the HVAC system, are as follows:

```
remote.control.00000SAMPLE001.C00000SAMPLE001_HVAC_1_switchBinary
```

For UC2-S01-4 (as it is show in Table 5): Control actions were sent by the BAM to the BIML and the specific load implemented the control actions successfully.

BAM integration with C-APP is still in progress. However, it needs to be mentioned that the optimizations are effective for certain users and waiting until the necessary amount of data is collected by the BAM to meet the needs of the remaining users.

2.3. UC3 Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting and optimization taking into account comfort boundaries, activity patterns and possible requirements.

This use case focuses on calculating at community/portfolio level, the demand elasticity, the degree to which energy demand can be changed, for example in response to energy prices.

Scenario S01 Building flexibility optimization.

The BAM runs a flexibility forecast optimization problem every day (day-ahead scenario) for the next day. The ODFM of the BAM runs the optimization using the trained models from the CDT. The CDT introduces the constraints, i.e., comfort boundaries, activity patterns, etc. and the flexibility of the day is estimated.

Forecasts are sent to the ECTs upon request.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

Table 6 Scenario S01 Building flexibility optimization.

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
CDT has user data	UC3-S01-1	Yes
ODFM runs flexibility forecast with user data	UC3-S01-2	Yes
Flexibility forecast to ECT upon request	UC3-S01-3	Yes
Visualize forecast	UC3-S01-4	Pending integration between the C-App and BAM

At the moment, the flexibility forecast for individual prosumers/consumers is available through the BAM endpoint under a day-ahead scenario and test evidence is shown in the annex using code [FT-31-02]

The BAM has been deployed at the commissioned pilot sites. This means that flexibility forecasts are available for ACCEPT users that have been commissioned at the Spanish and Greek pilot sites and for whom sufficient data (around three weeks) have been gathered to date.

Old test evidence from the ODFM is still shown in the annex using code [FT-31-01] but the integrated endpoint (point of communication) covers all the functionality.

There is still more work to be carried out for making the flexibility forecast available to the end user via the C-App.

Scenario S02 Building cost optimization.

User activates cost optimization SLA1 from the C-APP. The ODFM of the BAM runs the optimization using the trained models from the CDT. The CDT introduces the constraints, i.e., comfort boundaries, activity patterns, etc. Control dispatch data is sent to the BAM (a summary of each step for the scenario is found in Table 7).

Table 7 Scenario S02 Building cost optimization.

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
User request cost optimization SLA from C-APP	UC3-S02-1	Yes
CDT has user data	UC3-S02-2	Yes
ODFM runs cost optimization with user data	UC3-S02-3	Yes
ODFM control dispatch data sent to BAM	UC3-S02-4	Yes

The cost optimisation is currently performed on a manual basis for the commissioned ACCEPT users. The scheduler that will facilitate the automatic trigger of the BAM component for performing cost optimisations for the ACCEPT prosumers will be available on the cloud towards the end of August 2023.

Scenario S03 Comfort as a service¹

User activates cost comfort SLA from the C-APP. The ODFM of the BAM runs the optimization using the trained models from the CDT. The CDT introduces the constraints, i.e., comfort boundaries, activity patterns, etc. Control dispatch data is sent to the BAM (a summary of each step in the scenario is found in Table 8).

Table 8 Scenario S03 Comfort as a service

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
User request Comfort SLA from C-APP	UC3-S03-1	Yes
CDT has user data	UC3-S03-2	Yes
ODFM runs Comfort optimization with user data	UC3-S03-3	Yes
ODFM control dispatch data sent to BAM	UC3-S04-4	Yes

The comfort-as-a-service optimisation for individual prosumers/consumers is available through the BAM endpoint under a day-ahead scenario.

¹ SLA and comfort as a service terms are defined in the D5.1 [7] and D5.2 [6] deliverables.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

The BAM has been deployed at the commissioned pilot sites. This means that the comfort-as-a-service optimisation results are available for ACCEPT users that have been commissioned at the Spanish and Greek pilot sites and for whom sufficient data have been gathered (at least 3 weeks) to date. It should be noted that the comfort-as-a-service optimisation is in essence a version of the flexibility forecast which considers the narrow comfort boundaries² of the prosumer during occupancy hours.

There is still more work to be carried out for making the flexibility forecast available to the end user via the C-App.

2.4. UC4 Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation and analysis in community level.

This UC describes elasticity estimation at community level, this elasticity is required by the Retailer Tools (part of the ECTs in order to create energy tariff calculations which are used for use cases 9 and 11. Since this describes an internal process used as part of another use case check will be done in use case 9 which is referred to implicit demand response (DR) (UC9-S01-2 and UC9-S01-3) (see Table 14).

2.5. UC5 Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management for community self-balancing.

This UC concerns the management of district-level assets to provide them with flexibility capabilities based on forecasting and local control optimization.

Scenario S01 Regular Operation

ECTs send a community self-balancing request to the DAM. DAM generates forecast and generates self-balancing optimization in the storage forecasting module. DAM sends setpoints to the DILM (a summary of each step included in the scenario is show in Table 9).

Table 9 Scenario S01 Regular Operation

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
Generation forecast	UC5-S01-1	Yes
Storage forecast	UC5-S01-2	Yes
Demand forecast	UC5-S01-3	Yes
DER operation data	UC5-S01-4	Yes
Control Dispatch	UC5-S01-5	Unable to test
DILM setpoints to controllable elements	UC5-S01-6	Unable to test

We do not have controllable elements at this moment. We require access to controllable elements in order to test this scenario, which we hope to get before the end of the project. This will be reported in the third and last version of the integration.

2.6. UC6 Day-ahead smart charging flexibility via EV usage pattern profiling and forecasting.

Scenarios regarding control and usage of EV. Calculation off the flexibility available from EVs participating in the project. The forecasted flexibility considers the EV usage and charging patterns of the EV driver, their preferences and requirements. EV charging is expected to represent an important (and increasing) share of the electricity consumption, it is also however dispatchable, and can therefore prove very useful in demand-side management schemes.

Scenario S01 EV availability and charging data

C-APP request EV charger data to the DIML. User visualizes data in the C-APP (a summary of each step included in the scenario is shown Table 10).

² Narrow confort boundaries are used in the CDT which is explained in the D4.6 deliverable [5]

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

Table 10 Scenario S01 Regular Operation

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
DIML EV charger monitoring	UC6-S01-1	Partial check
C-APP shows data to user	UC6-S01-2	Not passing

Unable to test. We don't have this kind of data in the project at this point in time. We are trying with the Swiss demo in order to have an EV charger.

We have data from the Dutch demo which is captured by the DIML but the data access is limited to the electricity usage of the EV charging stations as a whole.

Scenario S02 EV charging profile

ECTs request data to the DAM which generates EV charge/discharge profile with DIML data (a summary of each step included in the scenario shown in Table 11).

Table 11 Scenario S02 EV charging profile

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
DIML EV charger monitoring	UC6-S02-1	Unable to test
DAM EV profiling	UC6-S02-2	Unable to test
ECT gets EV profile	UC6-S02-3	Unable to test

Since the last version of the integration deliverable, significant advancements have been made with regards to the inclusion of a community-used EV and EV charger (both V2G enabled) at the Swiss pilot site. AEM (Swiss pilot owner) has managed to secure that these assets participate in the ACCEPT project.

AEM has provided us with a list of available data types from the charger and the EV and there are currently discussions underway about the integration of the assets into the ACCEPT solution (as the assets are managed by a third party and for data protection purposes, the integration requires the creation of an AEM-developed secure internet connection the third-party system and the ACCEPT system).

As such, the test concerning the retrieval of the EV profile by the ECTs cannot be performed at the time of writing this report, but such tests will be performed for the last version of the integration report.

2.7. UC7 Community-level P2P flexibility/energy exchange based on locally produced renewable energy.

ECT executes P2P trading requests in 15-minute intervals. The ESCo passes the request to the P2P shadow administration to manage the process. Retailer Tools generate pricing signals and the ECFM generates portfolio level optimization, with this data the P2P shadow administration calculates the P2P energy price which is used by the P2P-EP along with data coming from the DIML and the BILM executes energy/flexibility verification smart contracts and settlement and remuneration smart contracts. Finally, the P2P-EP produces P2P trading credit notifications which the user receives through the C-APP (a summary of each step included in the scenario is show in Table 12).

Table 12 UC7 Community-level P2P flexibility/energy exchange

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
ECT executes P2P trading request	UC7-S01-1	Yes
Retailer tool generates pricing signals	UC7-S01-2	Yes
ECFM generates portfolio level optimization	UC7-S01-3	Yes
P2P shadow administration calculates the P2P energy price	UC7-S01-4	Yes
P2P-EP receives IoT data from DILM	UC7-S01-5	NO
P2P-EP receives IoT data from BILM	UC7-S01-6	NO
Energy/Flexibility Smart Contract	UC7-S01-7	Yes
Settlement and Remuneration Smart Contract	UC7-S01-8	Yes
User gets P2P trading credit notification in C-APP	UC7-S01-9	NO

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

Testing of UC7 was performed by initiating manually the flexibility and energy exchange from ECTs. Mock data were used for the pricing signal and the energy production and consumption values that are generated from the Retailer Tools and the ECFM accordingly. The log files below show the result of the manual testing and the data exchange between the aforementioned components. Logs and message exchanges shown in annex A using the code: [FT-71-01].

2.8. UC8 Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes.

Demand response schemes refer to the provision of ancillary services such as grid decongestion or to schemes involving demand control with pricing strategies. The main point is an active participation on the electricity market by demand side actors including retail. In the case of this use case when a DR event is triggered by the DSO, this UC requests flexibility information (potential) at prosumer and community level and proposes appropriate sequence of actions and collaboration among the available tools for the calculation and implementation of an optimal operational schedule of all available controllable assets. It therefore provides optimal DR solutions at community level, depending on the agreed role, i.e. Aggregator, Retailer, ESCo, based on inputs such as demand/generation flexibility. This kind of demand response scheme could be adequate for ancillary services seeking grid decongestion.

Scenario S01 Receive DR request

ASE (DSO Emulator) models network behaviour and creates a DR schedule. ASE request flexibility at community level from the Aggregator Tool. ASE sends DR dispatch to the AT (depending on network state at given time). The DR event will be notified to the user via the C-APP for user agreement. Finally, the AT sends a report with the DR actions actually performed (a summary of each step included in the scenario is show in Table 13).

Table 13 Scenario S01 Receive DR request.

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
ASE models network behavior	UC8-S01-1	Yes
ASE pushes DR schedule to the ECT	UC8-S01-2	Yes
Aggregator request ECFM optimization for community	UC8-S01-3	Yes
ECFM request flexibility forecast for BAM and DAM and creates optimization	UC8-S01-4	Yes
DR plan is used	UC8-S01-5	Yes Pending integration
Aggregator activates flexibility SLA	UC8-S01-6	Yes
User receives information about flexibility in C-APP	UC8-S01-7	Yes Pending integration
BAM executes flexibility for relevant assets	UC8-S01-8	Yes
DAM executes flexibility for relevant assets	UC8-S01-9	Yes
P2P-EP receives metering data and remunerates through SLA	UC8-S01-10	Yes
ASE receives verification of executed flexibility	UC8-S01-11	Yes

UC8-S01-1 and UC8-S01-2 (see **iError! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**) testing done both through Jenkins and manually at CIRCE. Message exchanges are shown in annex A using the code: [FT-81-01].

UC8-S01-4 for the BAM component is available through the endpoint shown in the annex in [FT-31-02]

For UC8-S01-8, the BAM receives the response from the Explicit DR event optimisation of the ECFM and follows the relevant operation schedule. For the former, the relevant endpoint is referenced in the annex A using the code: [FT-81-02].

The functionalities for the DAM and the ASE can be tested though the same endpoints that are used for integration testing. We are pending integration on the use of the DR plan and integration of the information in the C-APP which will be addressed in the last version of the document.

2.9. UC9 Participation in implicit Demand Response scheme.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

UC9 decides how to provide flexibility (i.e., which devices and for how long), based on dynamic network energy tariff and the flexibility forecast at prosumer and community level. In this case, the trigger for the DR event is the market electricity price. Hence, the most appropriate sequence of actions and collaboration among the available tools is established, in order in both end-user and community levels to participate in an implicit DR event.

Scenario S01 Implicit DR

ASE creates a day-ahead pricing schedule based on actual prices (market emulator) and network status (DSO emulator). ECTs and its subcomponents RT H-ECT and DEE generate elasticity estimation and tariff calculations. This schedule is passed to the BAM for cost optimization which generates setpoints for BILM devices. BILM sends metering data to the P2P Exchange Platform in order to remunerate DR according to SLAs (a summary of each step included in the scenario is shown in Table 14).

Table 14 Scenario S01 Implicit DR

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
ASE creates implicit DR schedule	UC9-S01-1	Yes
Pricing information is available from the ASE	UC9-S01-2	Yes
ECT generates portfolio elasticity estimation at community level	UC9-S01-3	Yes
Retailer Tool generates energy tariff calculation	UC9-S01-4	Yes
BAM calculates actions based on energy tariff (cost optimization)	UC9-S01-5	Yes pending integration
BILM implements actions	UC9-S01-6	Yes
BILM sends metering to P2P-EP	UC9-S01-7	Yes
P2P-EP remunerate through SLA	UC9-S01-8	Yes

UC9-S01-1, UC9-S01-2, UC9-S01-3 (see Table 14) automatically tested through Jenkins and manually checked at CIRCE.

UC9-S01-5 is a cost optimisation case. The cost optimisation is currently performed on a manual basis for the commissioned ACCEPT users. The scheduler that will facilitate the automatic trigger of the BAM component for performing cost optimisations for the ACCEPT prosumers will be available on the cloud towards the end of August 2023.

UC9-S01-4 has been tested manually and the results are show in [FT-71-01].

UC9-S01-6 is available through the control endpoint and test for it are show in the annex with code [IT-41-08]

UC9-S01-7 is available through the BILM endpoint: <https://projects.que-tech.com/api/data/%7bitemUUID%7d>

The item UC9-S01-8 (see Table 14) has already been tested under UC7-S01-8 (see Table 12).

2.10. UC10 Community flexibility bundling for local congestion management service.

Similar to UC8 and can be tested with the same test cases. The main difference is the requirements in terms of timings. This scenario requires an operation closer to near real-time and will have to be tested with synthetic data.

2.11. UC11 Retailer Day-ahead optimal pricing configuration for aggregated portfolio balancing.

ECTs and its sub-components RT and H-ECTs use information from the ASE to build energy tariff calculations for optimal pricing. This optimal pricing is used as part of UC9 (Implicit DR) as such UC11 is tested as part of UC9 (UC9-S01-1, UC9-S01-2, UC9-S01-3, UC9-S01-4) (see Table 14).

2.12. UC12 Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation for a cost-efficient district-level DER management.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

The DAM makes predictions on heating demand which are used by the ECT together with fuel cost data to calculate optimal schedule. ECT uses the calculated schedule to send setpoints to the DAM (a summary of each step included in the scenario is shown in Table 15).

Table 15 UC12 Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation for a cost-efficient district-level DER management

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
DAM heating forecast	UC12-S01-1	Yes
ECT generates optimal schedule	UC12-S01-2	Unable to test
ECT generates setpoints	UC12-S01-3	Unable to test
DAM /DIML dispatches setpoint to assets	UC12-S01-4	Unable to test

We were unable to test this use case as we have no controllable heaters available. This should be addressed in time for the last iteration of the integration.

2.13. UC13 Increase self-consumption at community level.

ESCo tool request to H-ECTs start of self-consumption optimization. Request flexibility forecast to the BAM and DAM. BAM requests user data to CDT. BAM requests data to BDT. BAM estimates flexibility forecast and returns it to H-ECT. H-ECT request forecast to DAM. H-ECT sends schedule to DAM. Schedules are applied and results visualized through the C-APP (a summary of each step included in the scenario is show in Table 16).

Table 16 UC13 Increase self-consumption at community level.

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
C-APP request	UC13-S01-1	Pending integration with BAM
H-ECT request data to BAM and DAM	UC13-S02-1	Yes
BAM forecast	UC13-S03-1	Yes
DAM forecast and asset data	UC13-S04-1	Yes
H-ECT self-consumption optimization	UC13-S05-1	Yes
H-ECT sends BAM optimal schedule for application	UC13-S06-1	Yes
BAM optimal schedule application	UC13-S07-1	Yes

For UC13-S01-2 and UC13-S01-3, the endpoint is tested in the annex with code [FT-31-02]

For UC13-S01-5, the self-consumption optimisation is currently performed on a manual basis for the commissioned ACCEPT energy communities. The scheduler that will facilitate the automatic trigger of the ECFM component for performing self-consumption optimisations for the ACCEPT energy communities will be available on the cloud towards the end of August 2023.

Item UC13-S01-4 can be checked though the integration testing for the DAM.

The item UC13-S06-1 (see Table 16) has been tested and the response can be found in annex A with code [FT-131-01].

The item UC13-S07-1 (see Table 16) has already been tested under UC2 and UC4

2.14. UC14 Active Citizen and LEC Engagement.

Nothing to test here. It describes engagement strategies not functionalities of any of the software /hardware components.

3. Functional testing by business case

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

This section is used to explain how the test created for the different use cases can also be used to test that the functionality of the business cases is fulfilled. We include small extracts from the business models document [3] in order to give a better context.

3.1. Business case 1

Energy Community as Flexibility Aggregator for Ancillary Service provision to System Operators and Balance Responsible Parties including network constraints management services, such as congestion management, and balancing services, such as frequency regulation.

The objective of this BC is to support the production and consumption of renewable energy by providing a solution that increases demand flexibility in order to address the issues arising from production (very variable) and demand mismatch.

Testing of this business case is covered by the testing performed for use cases 8 and 10. Use cases 1, 3, 5, 6 and 11 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

3.2. Business case 2

Energy Community as an Energy Service Company (ESCo) offering energy management services to community members, such as energy awareness and saving services and self-balancing on community level.

The objectives of this BC are to promote consumption of local renewable energy, to reduce the average consumption, to provide flexibility to the system and to provide information about energy market, energy production, energy prices and their forecasts.

Testing of this business case is covered by the testing performed for use cases 3 and 5. Use cases 1, 2, 6, 11 and 12 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

3.3. Business case 3

Energy Community as an Energy Service Company (ESCo) facilitating P2P flexibility trading (shadow administration):

The objectives of the BC are to involve community members in the management of the energy produced, to encourage consumers to reduce their consumption, to share their energy in return for payment, to enable the full exploitation of renewable energy and to reduce dependence on the grid.

Testing of this business case is covered by the testing performed for use case 7. Use cases 1, 3, 6, 7, 8, 11 and 13 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

3.4. Business case 4

Energy Community as a Retailer supplying the community members with energy models and potentially participate in the wholesale market the locally aggregated energy surplus.

The objectives of the BC are to increase the forecasting skills of the system, to obtain economic benefits from energy trading and from implicit Demand Response schemes and to ensure full utilization of the clean energy produced within the community.

Testing of this business case is covered by the testing performed for use case 8. Use cases 1, 4, 8 and 11 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

3.5. Business case 5

Energy Community optimized operation via P2P flexibility trading based on locally produced energy:

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

The objectives of the BC are to promote the consumers/prosumers to an active participation in the local energy market within the community and to increase their energy awareness. Moreover, other objective is to enable the understanding of Demand Response schemes by end-users.

Testing of this business case is covered by the testing performed for use case 7. Use cases 1, 2, 3, 4, 6 and 13 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

3.6. Business case 6

Heating-as-a-Service Provider models under schemes in which electric heating is utilized as a controllable load or alternatively through carrier coupling with DH networks leveraging the higher predictability of individual load behaviour to offer heating under predefined contractual terms.

The objective of this BC is to reduce energy consumption through the replacement of the old heating system, to reduce costs for heating service and to make the end-user active in his consumption decisions.

Testing of this business case is covered by the testing performed for use case 12. Use cases 1, 2 and 4 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

3.7. Business case 7

Prosumer engagement in Implicit Demand Response for local energy profile optimization (Time-of-Use optimization):

The objective of the BC is to gain flexibility for the energy system based to the variability of consumption according to the level prices. The other objective is to reduce the energy costs for every consumer provided with this service. Testing of this business case is covered by the testing performed for use case 9. Use cases 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 12 and 13 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

4. Automated Integration testing

Integration testing will be done only in interfaces between components with focus on automation. The idea is that by having automated testing we can ensure integration and avoid breaking changes within the different development cycles.

The goal is to achieve this by sending request to the different components using Jenkins and checking the response against the expected result. The first step is to gather the detailed definitions of all the payloads of the communications between components. We will use this to design test request for the different interfaces.

In this iteration more comprehensive test were performed with an increased focus in the payload content of the different elements and on the completeness of the exposed APIs.

In this section we have included a small text including an introduction of each component extracted from the architecture deliverable [1] for ease of understanding.

Most of the automation testing is done using an automation server called Jenkins which automatically performs the test in a daily basis. In it we also use a Junit plugging to analyse the output of the test and generate reports.

All test follow the same format, with tables for inbound and outbound messages (if relevant), a section and a table to show the completion of the test items as per the test design of each component.

In the case of the message tables, we have the following items:

- Data: A description of the data that is sent.
- To/From: the destination (or) origin component
- Payload Format: The internal structure of the message by type
- Communication protocol: The standard for the exchange of messages
- Destination Dev: The group responsible for the component at the other end.

4.1. Building Information Management Layer (BILM)

BILM is the component responsible for interfacing with the real world, by collecting metering, sensing and monitoring data from the physical assets of the building and processing it for further use from other components.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

Changes in respect to the last iteration of the integration task:

- Added integration with the C-APP.
- More comprehensive testing of the endpoints. from 6 to 14 items reported in the Junit plugging. Also includes tests for the control endpoint.

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Table 17 BILM outbound messages

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
IoT data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
IoT data	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful	QUE
IoT data	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
Building asset static data ³	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
IoT data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful	CERTH
Control actions	Building IoT infrastructure	JSON	RESTful	NONE

TEST DESIGN

We test the endpoint to get static configuration data from the prosumer (building asset static data) to get the devices it owns. Then we request IoT data from these devices and finally perform a test of the control endpoint.

We test 3 functionalities, the ability to get asset data, the ability to get IoT data and the ability to perform control actions. In the case of the control actions, we only test the existence of the necessary endpoint as the ability to act on particular devices is not relevant to the upstream functionality (it is however necessary to fulfil the functionalities) (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 17).

- Building asset data / IoT data / Control actions

Test run as part of the Jenkins postman collection, we authenticate, then send a request for information on the prosumers. With this information we query prosumers for their devices and then the devices themselves for IoT timeseries data verifying that each prosumer has a metering device. Finally, we also check the control action endpoint. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the codes: [IT-41-01], [IT-41-02], [IT-41-03], [IT-41-04], [IT-41-05], [IT-41-05], [IT-41-07] and [IT-41-08].

TEST STATUS

The test status for each item can be found in Table 18.

Table 18 BILM test status

TEST	Status
IoT data	Passing
Building asset data / IoT data	Passing
Control Actions	Passing

³ Such data refer mainly to the characteristics (attributes) of building-level assets.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

4.2. District Information Management Layer (DILM)

BIML is the component responsible for interfacing with the real world, by collecting metering, sensing, and monitoring data from the physical assets of the building and processing it for further use from other components.

Changes in respect to the last iteration of the integration task:

- Added AEM (Swiss demo) district heating data capture.
- More comprehensive testing of the endpoints. from 3 to 9 items reported in the Junit plugging.

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Table 19 DILM outbound messages

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Control actions	Available district-level IoT infrastructure	TBD	TBD	NONE
Metering and monitoring IoT data	District Asset Manager	JSON	MQTT	CIRCE
IoT data	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	MQTT	QUE
District assets static data	Energy Community Tools	JSON	MQTT	Hypertech
EV chargers location	Citizen App	JSON	MQTT	CERTH

TEST DESIGN

We test 3 functionalities, the ability to get IoT data, to send district static data and the ability to get EV charger location data. We will not test the ability to send control actions to the infrastructure as it is not necessary for the integration (it is however necessary to fulfil the functionalities) (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 19).

- IoT data

Test run as part of the Jenkins/postman collection, we authenticate, then send a get request and get metering data in return. We repeat the data request test for each of the demos. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the codes: [IT-42-01], [IT-42-02], [IT-42-03].

- static asset data

This endpoint is not built (we do not have static data)

- Weather data

This endpoint is not built (we do not have EV location data)

The test status for each item can be found in Table 20.

TEST STATUS

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

Table 20 DILM test status

TEST	Status
IoT data	Passing
static asset data	Not implemented
EV chargers location	Not implemented

At this point we are missing the asset static data to serve, as well as the EV chargers location. We have the Dutch EV chargers but they are not controllable and there is no use for their location.

4.3. District Asset Manager (DAM)

The DAM retrieves information on available district-level assets from the DIML and generates forecasts of their operation.

Changes in respect to the last iteration of the integration task:

- Added AEM DH (district heating) daily and hourly forecast.
- More comprehensive testing of the optimization results. from 13 to 46 items reported in the Junit plugging.

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Table 21 DAM outbound messages

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Control actions	District Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful	CIRCE
Optimisation results	District Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful	CIRCE
PV generation forecast	District Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

TEST DESIGN

We test the functionality of different combinations of the two parameters presented in the table above, site and type (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 21).

The context for these tests is the one described next: these tests check if the endpoint returns the requested file depending on the project pilot and the type of forecast that the user wants to get. The site is related to who is requesting the data (partners ESR or AEM), whereas the type of forecast depends on the time rate with which the data of the forecast files was generated (the hourly forecast refers to 4 predictions every 15 minutes within the same hour. On the other hand, the daily forecast refers to 24 predictions within the same day, each of one corresponding to an hour of the day).

This endpoint uses two different parameters. Those parameters let the user choose which location (project pilot) the data will be headed to, as well as the kind of forecast that has to be obtained.

The multiple cases will be described in the following points. In this iteration of the integration report we added additional checks for robustness existing endpoints have now 4 checks instead of 2

- ESR EV_forecast_hourly

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

With the site parameter set to ESR and the type parameter set to EV_forecast_hourly, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the hourly forecast for the electric vehicle consumption for the Netherlands pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-02].

EV forecast is part of the optimization results as per the Architecture document (D2.4 - ACCEPT business scenarios, use cases & requirements).

- ESR EV_forecast_daily

With the site parameter set to ESR and the type parameter set to EV_forecast_daily, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the daily forecast for the electric vehicle consumption for the Netherlands pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-03].

EV forecast is part of the optimization results as per the Architecture document (D2.4 - ACCEPT business scenarios, use cases & requirements).

- ESR PV_forecast_hourly

With the site parameter set to ESR and the type parameter set to PV_forecast_hourly, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the hourly forecast for the photovoltaic generation for the Netherlands pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-04].

- ESR PV_forecast_daily

With the site parameter set to ESR and the type parameter set to PV_forecast_daily, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the daily forecast for the photovoltaic generation for the Netherlands pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-05].

- AEM PV_forecast_hourly

With the site parameter set to AEM and the type parameter set to PV_forecast_hourly, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the hourly forecast for the photovoltaic generation for the Switzerland pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-06].

- AEM PV_forecast_daily

With the site parameter set to AEM and the type parameter set to PV_forecast_daily, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the daily forecast for the photovoltaic generation for the Switzerland pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-07].

- AEM DH_forecast_hourly

With the site parameter set to AEM and the type parameter set to AEM DH_forecast_hourly, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the hourly forecast for the district heating for the Switzerland pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-08].

- AEM DH_forecast_daily

With the site parameter set to AEM and the type parameter set to DH_forecast_daily, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the daily forecast for the district heating for the Switzerland pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-09].

- Control actions

We are unable to test control actions for the DAM component as there is nothing to control.

The test status for each item can be found in Table 22.

TEST STATUS

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

Table 22 DAM test status

TEST	Status
ESR EV_forecast_hourly	Passing
ESR EV_forecast_daily	Passing
ESR PV_forecast_hourly	Passing
ESR PV_forecast_daily	Passing
AEM PV_forecast_hourly	Passing
AEM PV_forecast_daily	Passing
AEM DH_forecast_hourly	Passing
AEM DH_forecast_daily	Passing
Control Actions	Not Implemented

4.4. On Demand Flexibility Manager (ODFM)

The ODFM constitutes the optimisation and control dispatch engine within the Building Asset Manager and comprises the Flexibility Forecasting Module, the Self-consumption Forecasting Module and the Control Management and Dispatch Module.

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Table 23 ODFM outbound messages

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Control actions	Building Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful	QUE
Profiling data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful	CERTH
Profiling data	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
Optimisation results	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

TEST DESIGN

We can't test control actions to DILM since it is not implemented. For now, we test optimization results (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 23).

- Control actions

Control actions were passed from the ODFM (in fact from the integrated BAM) to the BIML and implemented by the downstream building IoT devices/loads. This has also been described under the previous chapter.

This functionality was not accessible remotely and was tested on Hypertech premises.

- Profiling data

The test of sending profiling data to the Citizen App has not yet been performed. It will be performed once devices have been installed at participating households.

The test of passing profiling data to the ECTs has been performed. Flexibility profiles calculated by the ODFM have been sent to the ECTs (through the integrated BAM component). This has been covered in the previous chapter, under UC8 for example.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

This functionality was not accessible remotely and was tested on Hypertech premises.

- Optimisation results

Test run as part of the Jenkins/postman collection, we authenticate, then send a get request and get optimization results in return

The test status for each item can be found in Table 24.

Table 24 ODFM test status

TEST	Status
Optimisation results	Passing
Profiling data	Passing
Control actions	Passing

4.5. Consumer Digital Twin (CDT)

The integrated Consumer Digital Twin provides the trained models for the building and occupants to the ODFM for performing necessary optimizations. Tests performed for the ODFM on different optimisation scenarios have as a prerequisite the trained models from the CDT.

This functionality was not accessible remotely and was tested on Hypertech premises (see Table 25).

Table 25 CDT test status

TEST	Status
Citizen Digital Twin trained models	Passing
Building Digital Twin trained models	Passing

4.6. P2P Exchange platform (P2P)

The Community-level P2P exchange platform (P2P-EP) is a blockchain based and smart contract enabled platform that will primarily facilitate the exchange of energy and flexibility among community members in a trustworthy and transparent manner. It also allows the creation of Smart Contracts based on predefined Service Level Agreements, the Instantiation of Smart Contracts and the Instantiation of Smart Contracts

Test performed manually.

4.7. Citizen Application (C-APP)

C-App is a User Interface (UI) app composed of four main value-adding modules that aim to facilitate citizens engagement and cover energy, smart living, wellbeing, collaboration, mobility, to name a few, domains.

In terms of the functionality testing of the C-APP and more specifically the rest API services' responsiveness and context format correctness, we used pytest framework to develop individual scripts that guarantee the proper functionality of each sub-component. Internal algorithmic pipeline tests focus on the proper data acquisition, the algorithmic execution (time efficiency, context format).

Changes in respect to the last iteration of the integration task:

- Integration with the BILM.
- Remotely accessible version, in use by the pilots.

Except from the internal algorithmic functionalities, C-APP interacts with external components (BIML) to provide NILM results.

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

Table 26 C-APP outbound messages

Data	To	Payloa d Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
NILM	BIML	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

INBOUND MESSAGES

Table 27 C-APP inbound messages

Data	From	Payloa d Format	Communication protocol	Status
IoT data	BIML	JSON	RESTful	NO
Optimization results	BAM	JSON	RESTful	NO
Profiling Data	BAM	JSON	RESTful	NO
DR alerts	ECTs	JSON	RESTful	NO
Pricing Data	ECTs	JSON	RESTful	NO
EV Charger's location	DIML	JSON	RESTful	NO

TEST DESIGN

In this case we separate the test in two sections one test for the functionalities and a second section testing the communications with the BIML as this communication has the most user interaction.

TEST STATUS

Regarding the internal functionalities, the following table (see Table 26) displays the internal data services tests.

Table 28 C-APP test status

TEST	Status
Raw Data Visualization	Passing
Statistical Data	Passing
EV Charging Schedule	Passing
DR	Passing

The implemented tests mentioned in the table below are designed to cater to the specific needs of individual users. Each user may require different data from the BIML system, depending on their unique requirements and usage scenarios.

However, it is worth noting that some users might experience issues where the desired responses are not being received as expected. This could be attributed to inadequate communication between the BIML system and the citizens, leading to incomplete or inaccurate data retrieval.

Nonetheless, it's important to highlight that the response format of the BIML tool itself is correct. The BIML system is providing the data in the specified JSON format, as indicated in the table. Therefore, the issue lies in the communication process between the BIML system and the citizens, rather than the format of the responses themselves.

To address these communication challenges and ensure that users receive the desired responses, it may be necessary to investigate and improve the communication protocols and mechanisms between the BIML system and the citizens.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

In this version we had a remotely accessible version of the C-APP but due to GDPR and data ownership concerns we were not able to perform the test from CIRCE premises.

Table 29 BIML Communication Tests

Test Case	From	Description	Response Status	Format	Communication Protocol
RetrieveTokenTest	BIML	Retrieves a token for each user	200 OK	JSON	RESTful
Total Metering Consumption Test	BIML	Retrieves total metering consumption data from BIML	200 OK	JSON	RESTful
Generation Test	BIML	Retrieves generation data from BIML	200 OK	JSON	RESTful
User's Profile Test	BIML	Retrieves user's profile (location, id) from BIML	200 OK	JSON	RESTful
Per Device Consumption Test	BIML	Retrieves per device consumption data from BIML	200 OK	JSON	RESTful
Aggregated Consumption Test	BIML	Retrieves aggregated consumption data of total metering from BIML	200 OK	JSON	RESTful

4.8. Energy Community Tools

The Energy Community Tools (ECTs) include all components that interface or support the business cases of the market actors and/or the energy communities including optimisation and clustering engines.

In this iteration of the integration report, the integrated Energy Community Tools have been developed as a whole and most of the endpoints are exposed at this level instead of as discrete components as such we have added this section with all the new tests.

TEST DESIGN

We test the ability of the Energy Community tools as a whole to perform its functionalities. All tests are run as part of the Jenkins/postman collection. We perform the following test:

- Community Flexibility Forecast

A request for calculation of the flexibility of a prosumer is made. We check that we get a correct answer also checking that the request scope and the actual prosumer are correct.

- Community DR Event

We request firing a Explicit DR event and check that we get a successful answer.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

- Community DR Event per prosumer

We request firing a Explicit DR event for a prosumer and check that we get a successful answer.

- Community Energy prices

We request community energy prices and check that we get a successful answer. We also check that the answer contains a list of prices.

- Community Prosumer token balance

We request community prosumer tokens. We check that the response is successful, that we get the necessary identifiers regarding the community/prosumer and that the response contains a token balance.

- Community Prosumer SLA

We request community Prosumer SLA We check that the response is successful, that we get the necessary identifiers regarding the community/prosumer and that the response contains an SLA.

- Community Available SLA

We request Community Available SLA We check that the response is successful, that we get the necessary identifiers regarding the community/prosumer and that the response contains a list of available SLA.

- Community Initiate SLA

We request to initiate a community SLA We check that the response is successful and that the response contains a contract name for the initiated SLA

Test evidence is show in the annex with the codes [IT-48-01], [IT-48-02], [IT-48-03], [IT-48-04], [IT-48-05], [IT-48-05], [IT-48-06], [IT-48-07] and [IT-48-08].

4.9. Horizontal Energy Community Tools (H-ECTs)

The H-ECTs support all market role (i.e., aggregator, retailer and ESCo) specific functionalities of the Energy Community Tools.

For this version of the report all new test have been done in the integrated ECT which is the one exposing public endpoints so the tests below are from the first version.

The H-ECTs request flexibility data from the BAM (prosumer-level flexibility forecasts) in an automated format, using the following request:

<https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/lfmOrchestrator/prosumers/flexibility/forecast/9d7ba727-5cbf-11ec-9d97-960000500b98?period=15%20minute&startDate=2022-09-13T00:00:00.000-00:00&endDate=2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+00:00&flexibilityEstimationMethod=deltaP&baselineEstimationMethod=absoluteP>

The results of the flexibility forecast request are included in Annex A, under [FT-81-01].

The rest is described under the manual testing section.

4.10. ESCo Tools (ET)

The ETs suite consists of all functional level components addressing the needs of an ESCo⁴ (or an Energy Community acting as one).

⁴ Energy Service Company

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

For this version of the report all new test have been done in the integrated ECT.

4.11. Aggregator Tools (AT)

The ATs suite of tools includes all the computational engines that support the implementation of the explicit DR scenarios in the ACCEPT project, from the side of the aggregator.

For this version of the report all new test have been done in the integrated ECT which is the one exposing public endpoints so the tests below are from the first version.

INBOUND MESSAGES

Table 30 AT inbound messages

Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Optimization requests	ASE	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Table 31 AT outbound messages

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Verification of response	ASE	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

TEST DESIGN

The ASE sends DR requests to the Aggregator tool and the response provided by the Aggregator tool is given in Annex A, under [FT-131-01] (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 30 and Table 31).

The verification of response sent to the ASE by the Aggregator toolset after the DR dispatch was tested successfully (see Table 32). Evidence of the response can be found in Annex A, under [FT-81-01].

TEST STATUS

Table 32 AT test status

TEST	Status
Optimisation requests	Passing
Verification of response	Passing

4.12. Retailer Tools (RTs)

Although the retailer tools are part of the ECT they have separate public endpoints, so we keep separate test. In this version of the report new endpoints have been tested with RT output tunned to different demo sites.

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Table 33 RTs outbound messages

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
------	----	----------------	------------------------	-----------------

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

Optimisation requests	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP	Hypertech
Optimisation requests	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful	CIRCE
Pricing data	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful	QUE

TEST DESIGN

For now we test the pricing data message and the optimisation requests to the BAM (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 33).

- Pricing data, tested for the greek and spanish demo sites. Evidence on the annex with codes [IT-49-01] and [IT-49-02]
- Optimisation requests to BAM.

We send a get request for the pricing data and got a result. Additionally, an optimization request was sent to the BAM and the response was similar to the one examined under UC3.

TEST STATUS

The test status for each item can be found in Table 34.

Table 34 RTs test status

TEST	Status
Pricing data	Passing
Optimization requests to BAM	Passing

4.13. ACCEPT solution emulator (ASE)

The ASE is the component responsible for emulating the role of external to the energy community energy stakeholders, such as the DSO and the energy market operator.

Changes in respect to the last iteration of the integration task:

- Added endpoint to receive the result of the explicit demand response schemes.
- Integrated the ECT in the explicit demand response functionality.
- From 13 test items in the Junit report to 15 due to the added endpoints.

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Table 35 ASE outbound messages

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Explicit real-time DR Request	Energy Community Tools (Aggregator Tools, Retailer Tools and ESCo Tools)	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
Explicit DR Request	Energy Community Tools (Aggregator Tools, Retailer Tools and ESCo Tools)	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
Energy prices	Energy Community	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

	Tools (Aggregator Tools, Retailer Tools and ESCo Tools)			
Implicit DR Request	Energy Community Tools (Aggregator Tools, Retailer Tools and ESCo Tools)	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

TEST DESIGN

For a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 35.

An initial test that consists of authenticating and creating the security token for the next requests has been introduced. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-01].

- Explicit DR request (/drexplcit)

We test the functionality of different combinations of three parameters presented in the table above, date, scenario and real time.

The multiple cases will be described in the following points:

- Without any parameters, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the current hour. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-02]
- With an specific date/time parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the specified date/time. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-03]
- With a specific date/time parameter, scenario parameter and real time parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the specified date/time and the specified scenario from among a set of possible scenarios (real time parameter set to true). Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-04]
- With a specific scenario parameter and real time parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the current date/time and the specified scenario from among a set of possible scenarios (real time parameter set to true). Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-05]
- With a specific date/time parameter and real time parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the specified date/time (real time parameter set to true). Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-06]
- With a specific date/time parameter and scenario parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the specified date/time and the specified scenario from among a set of possible scenarios. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-07]
- With a specific scenario parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the current date/time and the specified scenario from among a set of possible scenarios. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-08]
- With the real time parameter set to true, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the current date/time. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-09]
- Implicit DR Request (/drimplicit)

In this case, the token used for the requests is the same as in the previous point, so no new token creation is necessary for this step.

- Without any parameters, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an implicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the current hour. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-10].

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

- With a specific date/time parameter and scenario parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an implicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the specified date/time and the specified scenario from among a set of possible scenarios. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-11]
- With a specific date/time parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an implicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the specified date/time. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-12]

With a specific scenario parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an implicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the current date/time and the specified scenario from among a set of possible scenarios. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-13]

- DR result (/dresult)

Two new endpoint have been added to allow the relevant stakeholders to post and read the result of a DR action. Test evidence is show with the codes [IT-412-17] and [IT-412-18]

- Energy Prices (/pricing)

In this case, two tests have been performed to test if the API correctly recognizes the date parameter. This parameter is used to specify which time window of 24 hours the user wants to obtain.

- If no date parameter is present when the request is made (this condition represents one of the tests), the energy prices (the 24 hours of the present day) for the present day will be returned instead. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-15]
- If a date parameter is present when the request is made (this condition represents the second test for this endpoint), the API will try to get the 24 hours window time that starts at the time specified in the request. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-16]

TEST STATUS

The test status for each item can be found in Table 36.

Table 36 ASE test status

TEST	Status
Explicit real-time DR Request	Passing
Explicit DR Request	Passing
Energy Prices	Passing
Implicit DR Request	Passing
DR result received	Passing

5. Manual Integration testing

In this section we list manual integration testing actions. The goal is to supplement testing efforts where automated testing in the previous section is not feasible.

At this point in time this section contains an example of manual testing for de DILM for illustration purposes (the DILM has also automated testing) and the test for the P2P platform which by its nature does not allow automated testing.

5.1. Building Information Management Layer (BILM)

Tests were performed automatically.

5.2. District Information Management Layer (DILM)

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

Table 37 DILM outbound messages

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Control actions	Available district-level IoT infrastructure	TBD	TBD	NONE
Metering and monitoring IoT data	District Asset Manager	JSON	MQTT	CIRCE
IoT data	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	MQTT	QUE
District assets static data	Energy Community Tools	JSON	MQTT	Hypertech
EV chargers location	Citizen App	JSON	MQTT	CERTH

TEST DESIGN

We test manually the IoT data functionality, making a get request and manually inspecting the result against the expected outcome (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 37).

- IoT data

Get request done using a testing tool. We check that the response code is 200 (ok) and manually inspect the json payload to check that it contains the expected data. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-52-01].

Although this test is also performed automatically this was added as an example of manual testing.

5.3. District Asset Manager (DAM)

Tests were performed automatically.

5.4. On Demand Flexibility Manager (ODFM)

Tests were performed automatically.

5.5. Consumer Digital Twin (CDT)

Tests were performed automatically.

5.6. P2P Exchange platform

Tests were performed automatically.

5.7. Citizen Application (C-APP)

Regarding the P2P Exchange Platform, it was tested manually in terms of receiving market inputs from the P2P Shadow Administrator and receiving and registering a Smart Contract enabled Service Level Agreement. The latter is a Heating as Service contract between a community member and the ESCo. The following figures show the successful testing of the aforementioned functionalities.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

POST http://127.0.0.1:5000/dispatchshadow

```

1  {
2    "partyId": "0x5E46E872A2e34D55E533A5d1a5C37b264f5431eF",
3    "partyRole": "Shadow Administrator",
4    "slaID": "0x283aEb845DeB45E21F4B1D6FD2CA3d6C76d6aC8",
5    "timestamp": "20220922001500",
6    "updatedKPI": [
7      {
8        "KPI": "p2p_price",
9        "KPI_value": "0.15000000000000002"
10     },
11     {
12       "KPI": "p2p_price_buy",
13       "KPI_value": "0.19"
14     },
15     {
16       "KPI": "p2p_price_sell",
17       "KPI_value": "0.15000000000000002"}]
18  }
19

```

Status: 200 OK Time: 7 ms Size: 208 B

```

1  {
2    "community_id": "1001",
3    "p2p_status": "True"
4  }

```

Figure 1 Dispatch of P2P energy price from the Shadow Administrator to the P2P Exchange Platform

POST http://127.0.0.1:5000/registerc

```

1  {
2    "slaID": "0x283aEb845DeB45E21F4B1D6FD2CA3d6C76d6aC8",
3    "parties": [
4      {
5        "partyId": "0x5E46E872A2e34D55E533A5d1a5C37b264f5431eF",
6        "partyRole": "ESCo"},
7      {
8        "partyId": "0x797b7c2971396fd02d4169Ae7159C280b23eD747",
9        "partyRole": "Community member"}],
10   "sla_startDate": "20220922001500",
11   "sla_endDate": "20221022001500",
12   "sla_description": "Heating as a Service",
13   "serviceLevelObjectives": [
14     {
15       "KPI": "Average Temperature",
16       "target_value": "18",
17       "rule": "more than",
18       "penalty": 100,
19       "penaltyFrom": "0x5E46E872A2e34D55E533A5d1a5C37b264f5431eF",
20       "penaltyTo": "0x797b7c2971396fd02d4169Ae7159C280b23eD747"}]
21  }
22

```

Status: 200 OK Time: 8 ms Size: 181 B

```

1  {
2    "success": true
3  }

```

Figure 2. Registering a Smart Contract on the P2P Exchange Platform.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

5.8. Horizontal Energy Community Tools (H-ECTs)

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Table 38 H-ECTs outbound messages

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Optimization results	P2P-EP	JSON	RESTful	QUE

TEST DESIGN

We manually tested sending optimisation results, as well as pricing data to the P2P-EP for carrying out P2P transactions (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 38).

- Optimisation results

We sent the optimisation results generated by the ECFM of the ECTs to the P2P-EP in a JSON format. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [FT-71-01].

5.9. ESCo Tools (ET)

No tests have been performed to date as the optimization requests sent by the ESCo tool to the C-App require that there is an active interface between the App and the ECTs. This will be tested in the next version of the report.

5.10. Aggregator Tools (AT)

This was covered under the automatic testing section.

5.11. Retailer Tools (RTs)

This was covered under the automatic testing section.

5.12. ACCEPT solution emulator (ASE)

Not done as all the functionalities will be tested automatically.

6. Integration schedule

Although most of the effort on the tools has been finished there is still some pending work on integrating the different tools together to achieve the best results. There is also some ongoing efforts towards adapting the prototype to the different demos by adapting the visualization, analytics and ML tools to the data and characteristics of the demos. Work on the final integration of the tools is expected to at least take until September while adaptations to the different demos are more dependent on the rollout to the demos themselves but could require some work until October.

7. Conclusions and next steps

In this iteration of the integration report we have seen significant upgrades in terms of the deployment of different tools in publicly accessible production environments such as the ECT, BILM and BAM as well as the C-APP joining the already deployed tools such as the RT, the ASE the DILM and the DAM. We have also seen significant progress in the integration of the different tools. For example, the integration between the ECT and the ASE as well as the integration between the C-APP and the BILM which allows users from the pilots to see their data, fully covering some use cases. We have also increased the quality of the test as the definitive payload of the messages and the needs of the solution became clearer.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

In the following months, as the last iteration of the integration task progresses the aim is to close the loop in the remaining functional test in which the test could be improved to better integrate and test the real needs of the prototype in conjunction to the experience gathered on the pilot sites.

8. Bibliography

- [1] ACCEPT, "D2.4_ACCEPT system architecture description v2".
- [2] ACCEPT, "D2.1 - ACCEPT business scenarios, use cases & requirements".
- [3] ACCEPT, "D2.7_Report on innovative business models and service contract design v1.1".
- [4] T. E. C. O. BEUC, "Electricity Aggregators: Starting off on the right foot with consumers," 2018.
- [5] ACCEPT, "D4.6 Citizen Digital Twin Model specification and design v2," 2023.
- [6] ACCEPT, "D5.2 – ACCEPT P2P Energy/Flex Exchange Platform_v2," 2023.
- [7] ACCEPT, "D5.1 – ACCEPT P2P Energy/Flex Exchange Platform," 2022.

9. Annex A

The goal of the annex is to store, when possible, the test as executed from a technical standpoint to serve as proof of what was performed. Since these tests are quite verbose and hard to follow for non-technical readers (most of them are messages intended for machine-to-machine communications) it was decided to store all of them here for ease of reading.

9.1. Functional testing

9.1.1. FT-21-01

The requests of the ECTs towards the BIML, for retrieving IoT and static data respectively, are as follows (UC1-S01-3):

- Request for IoT data:

```
curl -location -request GET 'https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93?startDate=2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z&endDate=2022-02-23T13:30:00.000Z&fillGaps=true' \
```

- Request for static configuration data:

```
curl -location -request GET 'https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/prosumers/a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93' \
```

A sample of the responses sent by the BIML to the ECTs can be found below:

ITEM
IoT data received from a heat pump at the Hypertech labs (UC1-S01-4):
<pre>{ "_embedded": { "TimeseriesData": [{ "value": "39.079", "startDate": "2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T12:29:59.999Z" }, { "value": "38.901", "startDate": "2022-02-23T12:30:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T12:44:59.999Z" }] } }</pre>

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

```

    },
    {
      "value": "39.112",
      "startDate": "2022-02-23T12:45:00.000Z",
      "endDate": "2022-02-23T12:59:59.999Z"
    },
    {
      "value": "39.328",
      "startDate": "2022-02-23T13:00:00.000Z",
      "endDate": "2022-02-23T13:14:59.999Z"
    },
    {
      "value": "38.88",
      "startDate": "2022-02-23T13:15:00.000Z",
      "endDate": "2022-02-23T13:29:59.999Z"
    }
  ]
},
"_links": {
  "self": {
    "href": "https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93?startDate=2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z&endDate=2022-02-23T13:30:00.000Z&fillGaps=true&page=0&size=100"
  },
  "timeseries-info": {
    "href": "https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93"
  }
},
"page": {
  "size": 100,
  "totalElements": 5,
  "totalPages": 1,
  "number": 0
}
}

```

Static configuration data from the Hypertech labs (UC1-S01-5)

```

{
  „prosumer-uuid“: „a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
  „prosumer-label“: „HypertechLab“,
  „prosumer-type“: „C“,
  „prosumer-country“: „GR“,
  „prosumer-global-loads“: [],
  „prosumer-spaces“: [
    {
      „space-uuid“: „1465dbd8-4393-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
      „space-label“: „LabSmallOffice“,
      „space-loads“: [
        {
          „load-uuid“: „727573ba-43ad-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
          „load-type“: „HVAC“,
          „load-label“: „Lab Central Heat Pump (ChM) (Phase 2)“,
          „load-items“: [
            {
              „item-uuid“: „e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
              „item-metric-type“: „Power“,
              „item-unit“: „W2“,
              „item-controllability“: false,
              „_links“: {
                „timeseries-data“: {

```

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

```

0024e84abf93"      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-
    },
    „timeseries-info“: {
0024e84abf93"      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-
    }
  }
}
]
},
{
  „load-uuid“: „727573bb-43ad-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
  „load-type“: „HVAC“,
  „load-label“: „Lab Central Heat Pump (ChM) (Phase 3)“,
  „load-items“: [
    {
      „item-uuid“: „e6e10f1c-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
      „item-metric-type“: „Power“,
      „item-unit“: „W3“,
      „item-controllability“: false,
      „_links“: {
0024e84abf93"      „timeseries-data“: {
      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6e10f1c-43ae-11eb-9464-
    },
    „timeseries-info“: {
0024e84abf93"      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6e10f1c-43ae-11eb-9464-
    }
  }
}
]
},
{
  „load-uuid“: „727573b9-43ad-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
  „load-type“: „HVAC“,
  „load-label“: „Lab Central Heat Pump (ChM) (Phase 1)“,
  „load-items“: [
    {
      „item-uuid“: „e6e10f1a-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
      „item-metric-type“: „Power“,
      „item-unit“: „W1“,
      „item-controllability“: false,
      „_links“: {
0024e84abf93"      „timeseries-data“: {
      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6e10f1a-43ae-11eb-9464-
    },
    „timeseries-info“: {
0024e84abf93"      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6e10f1a-43ae-11eb-9464-
    }
  }
}
]
},
{
  „load-uuid“: „5f3d11b0-4459-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
  „load-type“: „SENSING“,
  „load-label“: „Ambient Sensing Antonis“,

```

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

```

    „load-items“: [
      {
        „item-uuid“: „5e1efba2-445a-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
        „item-metric-type“: „Motion Alarm“,
        „item-unit“: „Motion Alarm“,
        „item-controllability“: false,
        „_links“: {
          „timeseries-data“: {
            „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/5e1efba2-445a-11eb-9464-
0024e84abf93“
          },
          „timeseries-info“: {
            „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/5e1efba2-445a-11eb-9464-
0024e84abf93“
          }
        }
      },
      {
        „item-uuid“: „5e1efba0-445a-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
        „item-metric-type“: „Temperature“,
        „item-unit“: „Celsius“,
        „item-controllability“: false,
        „_links“: {
          „timeseries-data“: {
            „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/5e1efba0-445a-11eb-9464-
0024e84abf93“
          },
          „timeseries-info“: {
            „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/5e1efba0-445a-11eb-9464-
0024e84abf93“
          }
        }
      },
      ...,
      {
        „load-uuid“: „7a60d5b9-4456-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
        „load-type“: „OTHER“,
        „load-label“: „Desk3 PC“,
        „load-items“: [
          {
            „item-uuid“: „e6491dd3-4456-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
            „item-metric-type“: „Energy“,
            „item-unit“: „kWh“,
            „item-controllability“: false,
            „_links“: {
              „timeseries-data“: {
                „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6491dd3-4456-11eb-9464-
0024e84abf93“
              },
              „timeseries-info“: {
                „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6491dd3-4456-11eb-9464-
0024e84abf93“
              }
            }
          },
          {
            „item-uuid“: „e6491dd4-4456-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
            „item-metric-type“: „Current“,
            „item-unit“: „A“,
            „item-controllability“: false,
            „_links“: {

```

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

```

    „timeseries-data“: {
0024e84abf93“      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6491dd4-4456-11eb-9464-
    },
    „timeseries-info“: {
0024e84abf93“      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6491dd4-4456-11eb-9464-
    }
  },
  {
    „item-uuid“: „e6491dd6-4456-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
    „item-metric-type“: „Power“,
    „item-unit“: „W“,
    „item-controllability“: false,
    „_links“: {
      „timeseries-data“: {
0024e84abf93“      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6491dd6-4456-11eb-9464-
      },
      „timeseries-info“: {
0024e84abf93“      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6491dd6-4456-11eb-9464-
      }
    }
  },
  {
    „item-uuid“: „166e5d78-4457-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
    „item-metric-type“: „switchBinary“,
    „item-unit“: „switchBinary“,
    „item-controllability“: true,
    „_links“: {
      „timeseries-data“: {
0024e84abf93“      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/166e5d78-4457-11eb-9464-
      },
      „timeseries-info“: {
0024e84abf93“      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/166e5d78-4457-11eb-9464-
      }
    }
  },
  {
    „item-uuid“: „e6491dd5-4456-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
    „item-metric-type“: „Voltage“,
    „item-unit“: „V“,
    „item-controllability“: false,
    „_links“: {
      „timeseries-data“: {
0024e84abf93“      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6491dd5-4456-11eb-9464-
      },
      „timeseries-info“: {
0024e84abf93“      „href“:      „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6491dd5-4456-11eb-9464-
      }
    }
  }
]
]

```

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

```

    }
  ],
  „_links“: {
    „prosumer-info“: {
      „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/prosumers/a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“
    }
  }
}

```

9.1.2. FT-31-01

ITEM

IoT data received from a heat pump at the Hypertech labs (UC1-S01-4):

```

{
  „_embedded“: {
    „TimeseriesData“: [
      {
        „value“: „39.079“,
        „startDate“: „2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z“,
        „endDate“: „2022-02-23T12:29:59.999Z“
      },
      {
        „value“: „38.901“,
        „startDate“: „2022-02-23T12:30:00.000Z“,
        „endDate“: „2022-02-23T12:44:59.999Z“
      },
      {
        „value“: „39.112“,
        „startDate“: „2022-02-23T12:45:00.000Z“,
        „endDate“: „2022-02-23T12:59:59.999Z“
      },
      {
        „value“: „39.328“,
        „startDate“: „2022-02-23T13:00:00.000Z“,
        „endDate“: „2022-02-23T13:14:59.999Z“
      },
      {
        „value“: „38.88“,
        „startDate“: „2022-02-23T13:15:00.000Z“,
        „endDate“: „2022-02-23T13:29:59.999Z“
      }
    ]
  },
  „_links“: {
    „self“: {
      „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93?startDate=2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z&endDate=2022-02-23T13:30:00.000Z&fillGaps=true&page=0&size=100“
    },
    „timeseries-info“: {
      „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“
    }
  },
  „page“: {
    „size“: 100,
    „totalElements“: 5,
    „totalPages“: 1,
    „number“: 0
  }
}

```

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.1.3. FT-31-02

POST v <https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/pfmOrchestrator/prosumer/flexibility/forecast/...>

Params Authorization Headers (9) **Body** Pre-request Script Tests Settings

● none ● form-data ● x-www-form-urlencoded ● **raw** ● binary ● GraphQL **JSON** v

```

1 ..... "uuid": "...",
2 ..... "flexibilityEstimationMethod": "absoluteP",
3 ..... "requestType": "explicit",
4 ..... "requestScope": "prosumerLevel",
5 ..... "prosumerUuid": "...",
6 ..... "assetUuid": "...",
7 ..... "startDate": "2023-06-05T00:00:00.000Z",
8 ..... "endDate": "2023-06-06T00:00:00.000Z",
9 ..... "period": "15 minutes",
10 ..... "intraDay": false,
11 ..... "createdAt": "2023-02-03T09:55:49.000Z",
12 ..... "unit": "W"

```

body Cookies Headers (5) Test Results St

Pretty Raw Preview Visualize **JSON** v

```

1 .....
2 ..... "requestInfo": {
3 .....   "requestType": "explicit",
4 .....   "requestScope": "prosumerLevel",
5 .....   "prosumerUuid": "...",
6 .....   "startDate": "2023-06-05T00:00:00.000+0000",
7 .....   "endDate": "2023-06-06T00:00:00.000+0000",
8 .....   "interval": "15 minutes",
9 .....   "flexibilityEstimationMethod": "absoluteP"
10 ..... },
11 ..... "baselineForecasting": [
12 .....   {
13 .....     "dtStart": "2023-06-05T00:00:00.000+0000",
14 .....     "dtEnd": "2023-06-05T00:15:00.000+0000",
15 .....     "mean": 0.0,
16 .....     "std": 2.5E-4,
17 .....     "unit": "W"
18 .....   },
19 ..... ]

```

9.1.4. FT-71-01

ITEM
The Retailer tools generated the following pricing signals
<pre> { "communityUUID": "", "startDate": "30/09/2022", "horizon": "24", "horizonType": "hour", "interval": "96", "intervalType": "minutes", "signalType": "energyPrice", "signal": [{ "value": 0.15 }, { "value": 0.15 }] } </pre>

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

```

        "value": 0.38
      },
      ...,
      {
        "value": 0.19
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

The energy production and consumption values that the P2P-EP requires from the ECTs have been generated as follows

```

{
  "requestInfo": {
    "uuid": "b9648eca-5815-44d4-9c2c-0ec4a103650d",
    "requestType": "explicit_production",
    "requestScope": "communityLevel",
    "communityUuid": "",
    "startDate": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000",
    "endDate": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000",
    "interval": "15 minutes",
    "flexibilityEstimationMethod": "",
    "baselineEstimationMethod": "absoluteP",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.420+0000"
  },
  "baselineForecasting": [
    {
      "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000",
      "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000",
      "mean": 0.0,
      "unit": "kW",
      "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.438+0000"
    },
    {
      "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000",
      "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000",
      "mean": 0.0,
      "unit": "kW",
      "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.440+0000"
    },
    {
      "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000",
      "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:45:00.000+0000",
      "mean": 0.0,
      "unit": "kW",
      "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.456+0000"
    },
    ...,
    {
      "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:30:00.000+0000",
      "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
      "mean": 0.0,
      "unit": "kW",
      "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.540+0000"
    },
    {
      "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
      "dtEnd": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000",
      "mean": 0.0,
      "unit": "kW",
      "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.540+0000"
    }
  ]
}

```

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

```

}
{
  "requestInfo": {
    "uuid": "b9648eca-5815-44d4-9c2c-0ec4a103650d",
    "requestType": "explicit_consumption",
    "requestScope": "communityLevel",
    "communityUuid": "",
    "startDate": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000",
    "endDate": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000",
    "interval": "15 minutes",
    "flexibilityEstimationMethod": "",
    "baselineEstimationMethod": "absoluteP",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.420+0000"
  },
  "baselineForecasting": [
    {
      "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000",
      "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000",
      "mean": 980.0,
      "unit": "kW",
      "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.438+0000"
    },
    {
      "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000",
      "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000",
      "mean": 980.0,
      "unit": "kW",
      "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.440+0000"
    },
    {
      "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000",
      "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:45:00.000+0000",
      "mean": 980.0,
      "unit": "kW",
      "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.456+0000"
    },
    ...,
    {
      "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:30:00.000+0000",
      "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
      "mean": 520.0,
      "unit": "kW",
      "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.540+0000"
    },
    {
      "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
      "dtEnd": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000",
      "mean": 520.0,
      "unit": "kW",
      "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.540+0000"
    }
  ]
}
}

```

The log files below show the result of the manual testing and the data exchange between the aforementioned components.

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

```

Market Successfully Initiated
{'start_time': 20220922000000, 'end_time': 20220922001500, 'p2p_status': 'True', 'community_id': 1001}

Requesting Energy Consumption and Production Values from ECFM...
Energy consumption and Production Values Received
{"start_time": 20220922000000, "end_time": 20220922001500, "type": "cumulative", "production": 100, "consumption": 200}

Requesting Electricity Prices from Retailer...
Electricity Prices Received
{"start_time": 20220922000000, "end_time": 20220922001500, "community_id": 1001, "price_buy": 0.07, "price_sell": 0.23}

Calculating P2P price
{"p2p_price": 0.15000000000000002, "p2p_price_buy": 0.19, "p2p_price_sell": 0.15000000000000002}
Market Completed
  
```

Figure 3 Log files UC7

9.1.5. FT-81-01

The item UC8-S01-4 which refers to the request by the Energy Community Flexibility Manager of the flexibility forecasts from the BAM and the DAM to carry out the optimization has returned the following response:

```
// 20220914104731
// https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/lfmOrchestrator/prosumers/flexibility/forecast/9d7ba727-5cbf-11ec-9d97-960000500b98?period=15%20minute&startDate=2022-09-13T00:00:00.000-00:00&endDate=2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+00:00&flexibilityEstimationMethod=deltaP&baselineEstimationMethod=absoluteP
```

It should be noted that the above request is for the flexibility forecast of the Hypertech energy labs office building (under the framework of early pre-validation tests), as the ACCEPT solutions have not been deployed to prosumers at the time of writing this deliverable.

ITEM

Response JSON:

```
{
  "requestInfo": {
    "uuid": "d3d9113c-1ee5-48be-a00e-2c977dcbd60f",
    "requestType": "explicit",
    "requestScope": "prosumerLevel",
    "prosumerUuid": "9d7ba727-5cbf-11ec-9d97-960000500b98",
    "startDate": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000",
    "endDate": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000",
    "interval": "15 minutes",
    "flexibilityEstimationMethod": "deltaP",
    "baselineEstimationMethod": "absoluteP",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.558+0000"
  },
  "baselineForecasting": [
    {
      "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000",
      "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000",
      "mean": 580.2,
      "unit": "W",
      "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.580+0000"
    },
    {
      "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000",
      "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000",
      "mean": 580.2,
      "unit": "W",
      "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.582+0000"
    },
    {
      "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000",
      "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:45:00.000+0000",
      "mean": 3.0,

```

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

```

    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.583+0000"
  },
  ...,
  {
    "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:30:00.000+0000",
    "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
    "mean": 640.4,
    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.671+0000"
  },
  {
    "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
    "dtEnd": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000",
    "mean": 640.4,
    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.672+0000"
  }
],
"flexibilityForecasting": [
  {
    "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000",
    "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000",
    "meanUp": 0.0,
    "meanDown": 0.0,
    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.580+0000"
  },
  {
    "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000",
    "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000",
    "meanUp": 0.0,
    "meanDown": 0.0,
    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.582+0000"
  },
  ...,
  {
    "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:30:00.000+0000",
    "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
    "meanUp": 0.0,
    "meanDown": 0.0,
    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.671+0000"
  },
  {
    "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
    "dtEnd": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000",
    "meanUp": 0.0,
    "meanDown": 0.0,
    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.672+0000"
  }
]
}

```

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

The above response includes values that cover all 24hours of the day for which the forecast was requested. Only a few values have been included herein for economy of space.

A similar process and message exchange is performed between the BAM and the ECTs. The ECTs may request the flexibility forecast of each prosumer by the respective BAM component using the same request.

With regards to the verification of response, which is sent by the ECTs to the ASE, the following message is dispatched:

ITEM
Response JSON:
<pre>{ "drEventID": "report1", "communityUUID": " d3d9113c-1ee5-48be-a00e-2c977dcbd60f ", "type": "absolute", "unit": "W", "aggregatedValue": "840.9" }</pre>

The item UC8-S01-10 has already been tested in the previous section on UC7 (UC7-S01-8).
The item UC8-S01-8 has already been tested under UC2 and UC4.

9.1.6. FT-81-02

```
{
  "name": "Community DR Event",
  "request": {
    "method": "POST",
    "header": [],
    "body": {
      "mode": "raw",
      "raw": "{\n  \"drEventId\":1,\n  \"startDate\": \"2021-12-13T00:00:00.000Z\",\n  \"drEventType\": \"test\",\n  \"durationPeriod\": \"15 minutes\",\n  \"intervalPeriod\": \"15 minutes\",\n  \"signalType\": \"test\",\n  \"signalUnit\": \"tets\",\n  \"signals\": [\n    {\n      \"value\": \"test\"\n    },\n    {\n      \"value\": \"test\"\n    } ]\n}",
      "options": {
        "raw": {
          "language": "json"
        }
      }
    },
    "url": {
      "raw": "{{baseUrl}}/gfmOrchestrator/community/drEvent/59cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b98",
      "host": [
        "{{baseUrl}}"
      ],
      "path": [
        "gfmOrchestrator",
        "community",
        "drEvent",
        "59cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b98"
      ]
    }
  }
},
"response": []
}
```

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.1.7. FT-91-01

The item UC9-S01-7 has returned the following (data are from the Hypertech Labs):

ITEM
Response JSON:
<pre>{ "_embedded": { "TimeseriesData": [{ "value": "230.045", "startDate": "2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T12:29:59.999Z" }, { "value": "230.581", "startDate": "2022-02-23T12:30:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T12:44:59.999Z" }, { "value": "230.637", "startDate": "2022-02-23T12:45:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T12:59:59.999Z" }, { "value": "230.527", "startDate": "2022-02-23T13:00:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T13:14:59.999Z" }, { "value": "229.522", "startDate": "2022-02-23T13:15:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T13:29:59.999Z" }] }, "_links": { "self": { "href": "https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/3cde1f48-ff56-11eb-9d63-960000500b98?startDate=2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z&endDate=2022-02-23T13:30:00.000Z&fillGaps=true&page=0&size=100" }, "timeseries-info": { "href": "https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/3cde1f48-ff56-11eb-9d63-960000500b98" } }, "page": { "size": 100, "totalElements": 5, "totalPages": 1, "number": 0 } }</pre>

9.1.8. FT-131-01

ITEM
Response JSON:
{

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

```

"communityId": "COM01",
"drEventId": 1,
"drEventType": "explicit ",
"startDate": "2022-12-09T13:00:00Z",
"duration": "1",
"durationType": "hour",
"interval": "15",
"intervalType": "minute",
"signalType": "delta",
"signalUnit": "Power",
"signals":[
  {
    "value":"+100"
  },
  {
    "value:"-100"
  },
  {
    "value":"+100"
  },
  {
    "value:"-100"
  }
]
}

```

9.2. Integration testing

9.2.1. IT-52-01

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

DILM / district data
📄 🗑️ ⋮

Method	URL	SEND
GET	https://localhost/diml/districtdata?site=AEM	

HEADERS	BODY	AUTHORIZATION	VARIABLES								
<table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 30%;">Name</th> <th style="width: 70%;">Value</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Authorization</td> <td>[REDACTED]</td> </tr> <tr> <td> </td> <td> </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Name</td> <td>Value</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Name	Value	Authorization	[REDACTED]			Name	Value
Name	Value										
Authorization	[REDACTED]										
Name	Value										

Response 200 OK
📄 942 B
🕒 31 ms

```

Server: nginx/1.15.8
Date: Fri, 17 Jun 2022 06:23:00 GMT
Content-Type: application/json
Content-Length: 787
Connection: keep-alive

1- {
2-   "measures": [
3-     {
4-       "label": "DN 80 out",
5-       "unit": "\u00baC",
6-       "value": 88.9
7-     },
8-     {
9-       "label": "DN 80 in",
10-      "unit": "\u00baC",
11-      "value": 80.1
12-     },
13-     {
14-       "label": "Energy",
15-       "unit": "kWh",
16-       "value": 2293433.0
17-     },
18-     {
19-       "label": "Power",
20-       "unit": "kW",
21-       "value": 459.6
22-     },
23-     {
24-       "label": "volume",
25-       "unit": "m3/h",

```

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.2. IT-41-01, User authentication

Iteration: 1 - User authentication

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** POST
- Request URL:** <https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/auth>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 355ms
- Mean size per request:** 2.29KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	b95c7fc7-76a3-4e26-b12a-4252a3baa997
Host	projects.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	35

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:15:15 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	2350
Connection	keep-alive
Cache-Control	no-store
Set-Cookie	KEYCLOAK_LOCALE=en; Version=1; Path=/auth/realms/iml-projects/; Secure; HttpOnly
Set-Cookie	KC_RESTART=; Version=1; Expires=Thu, 01-Jan-1970 00:00:10 GMT; Max-Age=0; Path=/auth/realms/iml-projects/; HttpOnly
X-XSS-Protection	1; mode=block
Pragma	no-cache
X-Frame-Options	SAMEORIGIN
Referrer-Policy	no-referrer
Strict-Transport-Security	max-age=31536000; includeSubDomains
X-Content-Type-Options	nosniff

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "access_token": [REDACTED],
  "expires_in": 3600,
  "refresh_expires_in": 2592000,
  "refresh_token": [REDACTED],
  "token_type": [REDACTED],
  "not-before-policy": 1649348617,
  "session_state": "1abe21a7-4b1e-43cf-abb1-5d94056f504a",
  "scope": "PilotPartnerAttributes"
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	T	Passed	T	Failed	T	Skipped	T
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.3. IT-41-02, Prosumer configuration

Iteration: 1 - Prosumers data

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://projects.que-tech.com/api/prosumers>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 431ms
- Mean size per request:** 1000.16KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	7a7decd2-63c1-4e38-aeaa-de06468f5e23
Host	projects.que-tech.com
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.18.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Tue, 30 May 2023 13:28:01 GMT
Content-Type	application/hal+json
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "_embedded": {
    "prosumerConfigurationList": [
      {
        "prosumer-uuid": "abacd279-a153-11ed-9da3-960000500b98",
        "prosumer-label": "ACGRR51",
        "prosumer-type": "R",
        "prosumer-country": "GR",
        "prosumer-global-loads": [
          {
            "load-uuid": "55cf4030-a3a5-11ed-9da3-960000500b98",
            "load-type": "DHW",
            "load-label": "boiler_consumption",
            "load-items": [
              {
                "item-uuid": "55f4b31a-a3a5-11ed-9da3-960000500b98",
                "item-label": "boiler_consumption",
                "item-type": "DHW",
                "item-country": "GR"
              }
            ]
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
test prosumer 1		1		0		0	
test prosumer 2		1		0		0	
Total		3		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

IT-41-03, Prosumer 1 building static configuration

Iteration: 1 - prosumer 1 building static configuration

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://projects.que-tech.com/api/prosumers/abacd279-a153-11ed-9da3-960000500b98>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 59ms
- Mean size per request:** 3.28KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="border: 1px dashed #ccc; height: 20px; width: 100%;"></div>
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	3d36bd0d-76b6-4bea-93ce-9fc7ccb8820e
Host	projects.que-tech.com
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.18.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Tue, 30 May 2023 13:28:02 GMT
Content-Type	application/hal+json
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "prosumer-uuid": "abacd279-a153-11ed-9da3-960000500b98",
  "prosumer-label": "ACGRRS1",
  "prosumer-type": "R",
  "prosumer-country": "GR",
  "prosumer-global-loads": [
    {
      "load-uuid": "55cf4030-a3a5-11ed-9da3-960000500b98",
      "load-type": "DHW",
      "load-label": "boiler_consumption",
      "load-items": [
        {
          "item-uuid": "55d305f9-a3a5-11ed-9da3-960000500b98",
          "item-metric-type": "Voltage",
          "item-unit": "V",
          "item-controllability": false,
          "item-value": 230
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
test has meter		1		0		0	
Total		2		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.4. IT-41-04, Prosumer 2 building static configuration

Iteration: 1 - prosumer 2 building static configuration

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://projects.que-tech.com/api/prosumers/c114c84c-9bdf-11ed-9da2-960000500b98>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 61ms
- Mean size per request:** 7.63KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	c309639a-2064-4726-a7ae-f620c02aef70
Host	projects.que-tech.com
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.18.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Tue, 30 May 2023 13:28:02 GMT
Content-Type	application/hal+json
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "prosumer-uuid": "c114c84c-9bdf-11ed-9da2-960000500b98",
  "prosumer-label": "ACGRR41",
  "prosumer-type": "R",
  "prosumer-country": "GR",
  "prosumer-global-loads": [
    {
      "load-uuid": "b6a2ea26-9d90-11ed-9da3-960000500b98",
      "load-type": "TOTAL METERING",
      "load-label": "total_consumption",
      "load-items": [
        {
          "item-uuid": "b6a2ea29-9d90-11ed-9da3-960000500b98",
          "item-metric-type": "Energy",
          "item-unit": "kwh",
          "item-controllability": false,
          "item-value": 0
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
test has meter		1		0		0	
Total		2		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.5. IT-41-05, Prosumer 1 data retrieval

Iteration: 1 - Provide IoT data prosumer 1 global meter (timeseries data) ▼

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://projects.que-tech.com/api/data/64ca1e15-a3a7-11ed-9da3-960000500b98?startDate=2023-03-08T00:00:00.000Z&endDate=2023-03-09T00:00:00.000Z>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 4s
- Mean size per request:** 9.37KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="border: 1px dashed gray; height: 40px; width: 100%;"></div>
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	439feb3f-bf2b-4097-abce-16f89d4b2bf3
Host	projects.que-tech.com
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.18.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Tue, 30 May 2023 13:28:06 GMT
Content-Type	application/hal+json
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "_embedded": {
    "TimeseriesData": [
      {
        "value": "378.188",
        "startDate": "2023-03-08T00:00:00.000Z",
        "endDate": "2023-03-08T00:14:59.999Z"
      },
      {
        "value": "376.306",
        "startDate": "2023-03-08T00:15:00.000Z",
        "endDate": "2023-03-08T00:29:59.999Z"
      },
      {
        "value": "389.076",
        "startDate": "2023-03-08T00:30:00.000Z",
        "endDate": "2023-03-08T00:44:59.999Z"
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
test timeseries items		1		0		0	
Total		2		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.6. IT-41-06, Prosumer 2 data retrieval

Iteration: 1 - Provide IoT data prosumer 2 global metera

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://projects.que-tech.com/api/data/b6a2ea29-9d90-11ed-9da3-960000500b98?startDate=2023-03-08T00:00:00.000Z&endDate=2023-03-09T00:00:00.000Z>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 65ms
- Mean size per request:** 9.28KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="border: 1px dashed gray; height: 40px; width: 100%;"></div>

User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	350a78b1-257e-4d1e-9010-1792a0bb0598
Host	projects.que-tech.com
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.18.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Tue, 30 May 2023 13:28:06 GMT
Content-Type	application/hal+json
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "_embedded": {
    "TimeseriesData": [
      {
        "value": "434.826",
        "startDate": "2023-03-08T00:00:00.000Z",
        "endDate": "2023-03-08T00:14:59.999Z"
      },
      {
        "value": "434.851",
        "startDate": "2023-03-08T00:15:00.000Z",
        "endDate": "2023-03-08T00:29:59.999Z"
      },
      {
        "value": "434.867",
        "startDate": "2023-03-08T00:30:00.000Z",
        "endDate": "2023-03-08T00:44:59.999Z"
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
test timeseries items		1		0		0	
Total		2		0		0	

9.2.7. IT-41-07, timeseries info / item configuration

Iteration: 1 - timeseries info / item configuration

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://projects.que-tech.com/api/items//64ca1e15-a3a7-11ed-9da3-960000500b98>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 53ms
- Mean size per request:** 440B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="border: 1px dashed #ccc; height: 30px; width: 100%;"></div>

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	a298ef1d-c8e6-48bd-a618-2330b5e4dbe0
Host	projects.que-tech.com
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS	
Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.18.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Tue, 30 May 2023 13:28:06 GMT
Content-Type	application/hal+json
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY	
<pre>{ "item-uuid": "64c01e15-a3a7-11ed-9da3-9c0000500b98", "item-metric-type": "Power", "item-unit": "W", "item-controllability": false, "_links": { "timeseries-data": { "href": "https://projects.que-tech.com/api/items/64c01e15-a3a7-11ed-9da3-9c0000500b98/api/data/64c01e15-a3a7-11ed-9da3-9c0000500b98", "rel": "data" }, "timeseries-info": { "href": "https://projects.que-tech.com/api/items/64c01e15-a3a7-11ed-9da3-9c0000500b98/api/items/64c01e15-a3a7-11ed-9da3-9c0000500b98", "rel": "self" } } }</pre>	
<input type="button" value="Copy to Clipboard"/>	

TEST INFORMATION							
							Search: <input type="text"/>
Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.8. IT-41-08, Control endpoint

Iteration: 1 - controlEndpoint

REQUEST INFORMATION

- i Request Method: POST
- i Request URL: <https://projects.que-tech.com/api/control>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- i Response Code: 200 - OK
- i Mean time per request: 55ms
- i Mean size per request: 78B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="border: 1px dashed #ccc; height: 40px; width: 100%;"></div>

Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	ab57e39b-0bf2-42e9-b982-30a0e52f5c7b
Host	projects.que-tech.com
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	80

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "itemUUID": "59cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960800500b98",
  "value": "25"
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```
{
  "code": "0",
  "status": "Success",
  "message": "The request submitted successfully"
}
```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.9. IT-42-01, Token creation

Iteration: 1 - token

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** POST
- Request URL:** <https://192.168.30.2/diml/token>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 125ms
- Mean size per request:** 278B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	2bd9b86d-6369-4d5d-9a40-1d440682e820
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	59

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 05:03:01 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	278
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "access_token": [REDACTED]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.10. IT-42-02, District data ESR

Iteration: 1 - District data ESR
▼

REQUEST INFORMATION

- i Request Method: GET
- i Request URL: <https://accept.fcirce.es//diml/districtdata?site=ESR>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- i Response Code: 200 - OK
- i Mean time per request: 175ms
- i Mean size per request: 1.78KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

Iteration: 1 - District data
▼

REQUEST INFORMATION

- i Request Method: GET
- i Request URL: <https://192.168.30.2/diml/districtdata?site=AEM>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- i Response Code: 200 - OK
- i Mean time per request: 10ms
- i Mean size per request: 787B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="border: 1px dashed white; height: 40px; width: 100%; margin-top: 5px;"></div>

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	d6621d60-1322-42ff-afbc-cab6f292573f
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Cookie	cookiesession1=678A3E136CF8940ACCB22EDB085B2BF0

RESPONSE HEADERS	
Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Tue, 30 May 2023 08:03:03 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1818
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "timestamp": "30.05.23 10:02:45",
  "measures": [
    {
      "label": "PAC",
      "unit": "W",
      "value": 89267
    },
    {
      "label": "PDC",
      "unit": "W",
      "value": 90479
    },
    {
      "label": "UAC",
      "unit": "V",
      "value": 230
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
AC power out		1		0		0	
power used		1		0		0	
PV yield day		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		4		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.11. IT-42-03, District data AEM

Iteration: 1 - District data AEM

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/diml/districtdata?site=AEM>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 57ms
- Mean size per request:** 1.85KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="border: 1px dashed gray; height: 20px; width: 100%;"></div>
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	918fd204-135c-41ed-b932-da2261a6b3f4
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Cookie	cookiesession1=678A3E136CF8940ACCB22EDB085B2BF0

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Tue, 30 May 2023 08:03:02 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1891
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "measures": [
    {
      "label": "DISTRICT HEATING: Hot Water Out",
      "unit": "°C",
      "value": "85.4"
    },
    {
      "label": "DISTRICT HEATING: Cold Water In",
      "unit": "°C",
      "value": "74.8"
    },
    {
      "label": "DISTRICT HEATING: Power",
      "unit": "kW",
      "value": "66.0"
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
boiler power		1		0		0	
heating power		1		0		0	
hot water out		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		4		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.12. IT-43-01, Token creation

Iteration: 1 - Create token

REQUEST INFORMATION

- i Request Method: POST
- i Request URL: <https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/token>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- i Response Code: 200 - OK
- i Mean time per request: 225ms
- i Mean size per request: 278B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	7ee33778-5ad2-4a2d-bce7-f68380d47075
Host	20.216.174.110
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	59

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "username": "devC1rce",
  "password": "J1NT8gedtW3hokPQ7hrs"
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:57:01 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	278
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "access_token": [REDACTED]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.13. IT-43-02, Get data (with ESR as site parameter and EV_forecast_hourly as type parameter)

Iteration: 1 - Get data (site = ESR and type = EV_forecast_hourly)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=ESR&type=EV_forecast_hourly

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 35ms
- Mean size per request:** 536B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="border: 1px dashed gray; height: 20px; width: 100%;"></div>
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	a6af9ece-1fd5-4f7c-ace1-9b09c267b879
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Cookie	cookiesession1=678A3E13B18AA7EB69882A38FFF501E1

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 29 May 2023 10:29:56 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	537
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "Date": "2023-05-16",
  "Demo.id": "NED",
  "Asset_name": "EV",
  "Data": "Hour-Ahead Generation Forecast",
  "Data_Type": "Array",
  "Values": [
    {
      "Time": "09:47:36.214659",
      "Value [kW]": 0.007
    },
    {
      "Time": "10:02:36.214659",
      "Value [kW]": 0.008
    },
    {
      "Time": "10:17:36.214659",
      "Value [kW]": 0.008
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
contains data	1	0	0
data is correct	1	0	0
location is correct	1	0	0
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	4	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.14. IT-43-03, Get data (with ESR as site parameter and EV_forecast_daily as type parameter)

Iteration: 1 - Get data (site = ESR and type = EV_forecast_daily) ▼

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=ESR&type=EV_forecast_daily

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 37ms
- Mean size per request:** 2.32KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="border: 1px dashed gray; height: 30px; width: 100%;"></div>
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	a6af9ece-1fd5-4f7c-ace1-9b09c267b879
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Cookie	cookiesession1=678A3E13B18AA7EB69882A38FFF501E1

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 29 May 2023 10:29:56 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	2377
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

"Values": [
  {
    "Time": "10:32:36.214659",
    "Value [kW]": 0.012
  },
  {
    "Time": "11:32:36.214659",
    "Value [kW]": 0.007
  },
  {
    "Time": "12:32:36.214659",
    "Value [kW]": 0.005
  },
  {
    "Time": "13:32:36.214659",
    "Value [kW]": 0.004
  }
]

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
contains data		1		0		0	
data is correct		1		0		0	
location is correct		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		4		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.15. IT-43-04, Get data (with ESR as site parameter and PV_forecast_hourly as type parameter)

Iteration: 1 - Get data (site = ESR and type = PV_forecast_hourly)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=ESR&type=PV_forecast_hourly

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 33ms
- Mean size per request:** 568B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="background-color: black; width: 100%; height: 20px;"></div>
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	31991b5b-5b3d-4bf5-adc5-fe7c9d3939c5
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Cookie	cookiesession1=678A3E13B18AA7EB69882A38FFF501E1

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 29 May 2023 10:29:56 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	584
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "Date": "2023-05-16",
  "Demo:id": "NED",
  "Asset_name": "PV",
  "Data": "Day-Ahead Generation Forecast",
  "Data_Type": "Array",
  "Values": [
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 09:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 117.323
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 10:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 10:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 10:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 10:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 11:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 11:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 11:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 11:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 12:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 12:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 12:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 12:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 13:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 13:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 13:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 13:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 14:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 14:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 14:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 14:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 15:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 15:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 15:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 15:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 16:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 16:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 16:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 16:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 17:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 17:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 17:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 17:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 18:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 18:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 18:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 18:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 19:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 19:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 19:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 19:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 20:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 20:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 20:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 20:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 21:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 21:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 21:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 21:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 22:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 22:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 22:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 22:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 23:00:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 23:15:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 23:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 23:45:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 124.417
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
contains data		1		0		0	
data is correct		1		0		0	
location is correct		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		4		0		0	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957781.

82

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.16. IT-43-05, Get data (with ESR as site parameter and PV_forecast_daily as type parameter)

Iteration: 1 - Get data (site = ESR and type = PV_forecast_daily) ✓

REQUEST INFORMATION	RESPONSE INFORMATION
Request Method: GET Request URL: https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=ESR&type=PV_forecast_daily	Response Code: 200 - OK Mean time per request: 34ms Mean size per request: 2.54KB
TEST PASS PERCENTAGE 100 %	

REQUEST HEADERS	
Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="border: 1px solid black; height: 20px; width: 100%; background-color: black;"></div>
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	0ff447c7-f9c3-4f96-8149-36c1651069ad
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Cookie	cookiesession1=678A3E13790969B2A06F963CA592CC15

RESPONSE HEADERS	
Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 29 May 2023 11:24:19 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	2612
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "Date": "2023-05-16",
  "Demo:id": "NED",
  "Asset_name": "PV",
  "Data": "Day-Ahead Generation Forecast",
  "Data_Type": "Array",
  "Values": [
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 10:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 133.484
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 11:30:01+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 137.718
    },
    {

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
contains data		1		0		0	
data is correct		1		0		0	
location is correct		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		4		0		0	

Go

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.17. IT-43-06, Get data (with AEM as site parameter and PV_forecast_hourly as type parameter)

Iteration: 1 - Get data (site = AEM and type = PV_forecast_hourly)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=AEM&type=PV_forecast_hourly

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 34ms
- Mean size per request:** 568B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="background-color: black; width: 100%; height: 20px;"></div>
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	ed7c8ca9-b507-4968-8f1a-232a796c4dc7
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Cookie	cookiesession1=678A3E13790969B2A06F963CA592CC15

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 29 May 2023 11:24:19 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	581
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "Date": "2023-05-17",
  "Demo.id": "SUT",
  "Asset_name": "DH",
  "Data": "Hour-Ahead Demand Forecast",
  "Data_Type": "Array",
  "Values": [
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-17 12:45:01+02:00",
      "Baseline [kw]": "[0.05516651]",
      "Maximum [kw]": "[0.10437386]",
      "Minimum [kw]": "[0.02995415]"
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-17 13:00:01+02:00",
      "Baseline [kw]": "[0.03845014]",
      "Maximum [kw]": "[0.07790028]"
    }
  ]
}

```

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
contains data		1		0		0	
data is correct		1		0		0	
location is correct		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		4		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.18. IT-43-07, Get data (with AEM as site parameter and PV_forecast_daily as type parameter)

Iteration: 1 - Get data (site = AEM and type = PV_forecast_daily) ▼

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=AEM&type=PV_forecast_daily

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 33ms
- Mean size per request:** 2.53KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="background-color: black; width: 100%; height: 1.2em; margin-top: 2px;"></div>
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	2fe0f6c2-9679-412b-96ab-8db6303aa51e
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Cookie	cookiesession1=678A3E13790969B2A06F963CA592CC15

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 29 May 2023 11:24:19 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	2603
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "Date": "2023-05-16",
  "Demo:id": "SUI",
  "Asset_name": "PV",
  "Data": "Day-Ahead Generation Forecast",
  "Data_Type": "Array",
  "Values": [
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 10:30:02+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 21.892
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-16 11:30:02+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 26.083
    },
    {

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
contains data		1		0		0	
data is correct		1		0		0	
location is correct		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		4		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.19. IT-43-08, Get data (with AEM as site parameter and DH_forecast_hourly as type parameter)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- i Request Method: GET
- i Request URL: https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=AEM&type=DH_forecast_hourly

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- i Response Code: 200 - OK
- i Mean time per request: 54ms
- i Mean size per request: 972B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="background-color: black; height: 20px; width: 100%;"></div>
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	3bc323e1-e243-4704-b588-feabac813017
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Cookie	cookiesession1=678A3E13790969B2A06F963CA592CC15

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 29 May 2023 11:24:19 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	972
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "Date": "2023-05-17",
  "Demo:id": "SUI",
  "Asset_name": "DH",
  "Data": "Hour-Ahead Demand Forecast",
  "Data_Type": "Array",
  "Values": [
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-17 12:45:01+02:00",
      "Baseline [kW]": "[0.09516051]",
      "Maximum [kW]": "[0.10437386]",
      "Minimum [kW]": "[0.02095415]"
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-17 13:00:01+02:00",
      "Baseline [kW]": "[0.03845014]",
      "Maximum [kW]": "[0.04333333]",
      "Minimum [kW]": "[0.02095415]"
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
contains data		1		0		0	
data is correct		1		0		0	
location is correct		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		4		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.20. IT-43-08, Get data (with AEM as site parameter and DH_forecast_daily as type parameter)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- i Request Method: GET
- i Request URL: https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=AEM&type=DH_forecast_daily

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- i Response Code: 200 - OK
- i Mean time per request: 57ms
- i Mean size per request: 5.27KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer <div style="background-color: black; width: 100%; height: 20px; margin-top: 5px;"></div>
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	09db509b-c310-448a-84c7-ba76baceaa06
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Cookie	cookiesession1=678A3E13790969B2A06F963CA592CC15

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 29 May 2023 11:24:19 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	5396
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "Date": "2023-05-17",
  "Demo:id": "SUI",
  "Asset_name": "DH",
  "Data": "Day-Ahead Demand Forecast",
  "Data_Type": "Array",
  "Values": [
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-17 13:30:01+02:00",
      "Baseline [kW]": 0.02123334479622436,
      "Maximum [kW]": 0.03918279861289748,
      "Minimum [kW]": 0.011821718908856273
    },
    {
      "Time": "2023-05-17 14:30:01+02:00",
      "Baseline [kW]": 0.02123334479622436,
      "Maximum [kW]": 0.03918279861289748,
      "Minimum [kW]": 0.011821718908856273
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
contains data		1		0		0	
data is correct		1		0		0	
location is correct		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		4		0		0	

9.2.21. IT-48-01, Community Flexibility Forecast

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

Iteration: 1 - Community Flexibility Forecast

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** POST
- Request URL:** <https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/gfmOrchestrator/community/flexibility/forecast/a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 309ms
- Mean size per request:** 184B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	bb2aaf00-1c39-4878-b31e-486a38bb853d
Host	services.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	206

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "period": "15 minutes",
  "startDate": "2020-03-06T00:00:00.000Z",
  "endDate": "2020-03-06T00:30:00.000Z",
  "flexibilityEstimationMethod": "absoluteP",
  "baselineEstimationMethod": "absoluteP"
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Fri, 02 Jun 2023 08:13:04 GMT
Content-Type	application/json;charset=UTF-8
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "requestInfo": {
    "requestType": "explicit",
    "requestScope": "prosumerLevel",
    "prosumerUuid": "a9446c6b-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93"
  },
  "baselineForecasting": null,
  "flexibilityForecasting": null
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
prosumer is correct	1	0	0
requestScope is correct	1	0	0
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	3	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

IT-48-02, Community DR Event

Iteration: 1 - Community DR Event

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** POST
- Request URL:** <https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/gfmOrchestrator/community/drEvent/a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 100ms
- Mean size per request:** 7B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	845e4cd4-d25f-4432-b67e-b936d4921b39
Host	services.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	326

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "drEventId": 1,
  "startDate": "2023-12-13T00:00:00.000Z",
  "drEventType": "explicit",
  "durationPeriod": "15 minutes",
  "intervalPeriod": "15 minutes",
  "signalType": "test",
  "signalUnit": "test",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": "test"
    },
    {
      "value": "test"
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Fri, 02 Jun 2023 08:13:04 GMT
Content-Type	text/plain;charset=ISO-8859-1
Content-Length	7
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

Success

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.22. IT-48-03, Community DR Event per Prosumer

Iteration: 1 - Community DR Event per Prosumer

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** POST
- Request URL:** <https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/gfmOrchestrator/community/drEvent/a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 101ms
- Mean size per request:** 7B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	f361e976-fc45-4401-9694-fb608aed2479
Host	services.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	322

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "drEventId": 1,
  "startDate": "2021-12-13T00:00:00.000Z",
  "drEventType": "test",
  "durationPeriod": "15 minutes",
  "intervalPeriod": "15 minutes",
  "signalType": "test",
  "signalUnit": "tests",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": "test"
    },
    {
      "value": "test"
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Fri, 02 Jun 2023 08:13:04 GMT
Content-Type	text/plain;charset=ISO-8859-1
Content-Length	7
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

Success

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957781.

99

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.23. IT-48-04, Community Energy Prices

Iteration: 1 - Community Energy Prices

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** POST
- Request URL:** <https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/gfmOrchestrator/community/getEnergyPrices/a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 103ms
- Mean size per request:** 362B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	e9eaa6c1-0386-473e-beb6-17f28f33a13d
Host	services.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	543

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "type": "type",
  "startDate": "2021-12-13T00:00:00.000Z",
  "endDate": "test",
  "interval": "15 minutes",
  "createdAt": "15 minutes",
  "energyPriceList": [
    {
      "start": "test",
      "end": "end",
      "buyPrice": 2.3,
      "feedInPrice": 2.5,
      "priceUnit": "priceUnit",
      "createdAt": "15 minutes"
    },
    {

```

[Copy to Clipboard](#)

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Sun, 04 Jun 2023 08:13:05 GMT
Content-Type	application/json;charset=UTF-8
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "type": "type",
  "startDate": "2021-12-13T00:00:00.000Z",
  "endDate": "test",
  "interval": "15 minutes",
  "createdAt": "15 minutes",
  "energyPriceList": [
    {
      "start": "test",
      "end": "end",
      "buyPrice": 2.3,
      "feedInPrice": 2.5,
      "priceUnit": "priceUnit",
      "createdAt": "15 minutes"
    },
    {

```

[Copy to Clipboard](#)

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
has pricing data	1	0	0
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	2	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.24. IT-48-05, Community prosumer token balance

Iteration: 1 - Community Prosumer token balance

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/gfmOrchestrator/community/getProsumerTokenBalance/59cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b98/68cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b56>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 102ms
- Mean size per request:** 214B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	8298ba8d-e772-4552-9374-fd7f52a55499
Host	services.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	543

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "type": "type",
  "startDate": "2021-12-13T00:00:00.000Z",
  "endDate": "test",
  "interval": "15 minutes",
  "createdAt": "15 minutes",
  "energyPriceList": [
    {
      "start": "test",
      "end": "end",
      "buyPrice": 2.3,
      "feedInPrice": 2.5,
      "priceUnit": "priceUnit",
      "createdAt": "15 minutes"
    }
  ],
  {

```

Copy to Clipboard

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Sun, 04 Jun 2023 08:13:05 GMT
Content-Type	application/json;charset=UTF-8
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```
{
  "communityUUID": "59cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b98",
  "prosumerUUID": "68cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b56",
  "prosumerAddress": "0xc5d2460186f7233c927e7db2dcc703c0e500b653ca82273b7bfad8045d85a470",
  "balance": 3456
}
```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
has balance		1		0		0	
has community UUID		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		3		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.25. IT-48-06, Community prosumer SLA

Iteration: 1 - Community Prosumer SLA

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/gfmOrchestrator/community/getProsumerSLA/59cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b98/68cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b56>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 104ms
- Mean size per request:** 393B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	ef0edf1d-01b4-46f5-8800-eceb41cd3ae4
Host	services.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	543

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "type": "type",
  "startDate": "2021-12-13T00:00:00.000Z",
  "endDate": "test",
  "interval": "15 minutes",
  "createdAt": "15 minutes",
  "energyPriceList": [
    {
      "start": "test",
      "end": "end",
      "buyPrice": 2.3,
      "feedInPrice": 2.5,
      "priceUnit": "priceUnit",
      "createdAt": "15 minutes"
    }
  ],
  {

```

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Sun, 04 Jun 2023 08:13:05 GMT
Content-Type	application/json;charset=UTF-8
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "communityUUID": "59cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b08",
  "prosumerUUID": "68cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b56",
  "prosumerAddress": "0xc5d2460186f7233c927e7db2dccc703c0e500b653ca82273b7bfad8045d85a470",
  "slaContractList": [
    {
      "contractName": "Market",
      "contractDescription": "Set a brief description of the contract",
      "contractAddress": "0x2E7D95Fe38438cDcFac99bF82D6793814303032c",
      "contractFunds": 2345
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓ Passed	↑↓ Failed	↑↓ Skipped
has community UUID	1	0	0
has sla	1	0	0
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	3	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.26. IT-48-07, Community available SLA

Iteration: 1 - Community Available SLA

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/gfmOrchestrator/community/getProsumerSLA/59cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b98/68cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b56>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 104ms
- Mean size per request:** 393B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	9b5dc3d9-3e76-4bab-bc90-07829fa6898f
Host	services.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	543

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "type": "type",
  "startDate": "2021-12-13T00:00:00.000Z",
  "endDate": "test",
  "interval": "15 minutes",
  "createdAt": "15 minutes",
  "energyPriceList": [
    {
      "start": "test",
      "end": "end",
      "buyPrice": 2.3,
      "feedInPrice": 2.5,
      "priceUnit": "priceUnit",
      "createdAt": "15 minutes"
    },
    {

```

Copy to Clipboard

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Sun, 04 Jun 2023 08:13:05 GMT
Content-Type	application/json;charset=UTF-8
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "communityUUID": "59cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b98",
  "prosumerUUID": "68cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b56",
  "prosumerAddress": "0xc5d2460186f7233c927e7db2dcc703c0e500b653ca82273b7bfad8045d85a470",
  "slaContractList": [
    {
      "contractName": "Market",
      "contractDescription": "Set a brief description of the contract",
      "contractAddress": "0x2E7D95Fe3843BcDcfaC99bF820b793814303032c",
      "contractFunds": 2345
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
has community UUID		1		0		0	
has sla		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		3		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.27. IT-48-08, Community initiate SLA

Iteration: 1 - Community Initiate SLA

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** POST
- Request URL:** <https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/gfmOrchestrator/community/initiateSLA/59cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b98/68cc878e-9d93-11ed-9da3-960000500b56>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 102ms
- Mean size per request:** 181B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	3e6dd0f9-161e-4472-8119-9f352d4719f5
Host	services.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	543

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "type": "type",
  "startDate": "2021-12-13T00:00:00.000Z",
  "endDate": "test",
  "interval": "15 minutes",
  "createdAt": "15 minutes",
  "energyPriceList": [
    {
      "start": "test",
      "end": "end",
      "buyPrice": 2.3,
      "feedInPrice": 2.5,
      "priceUnit": "priceUnit",
      "createdAt": "15 minutes"
    },
    {
      "start": "test",
      "end": "end",
      "buyPrice": 2.3,
      "feedInPrice": 2.5,
      "priceUnit": "priceUnit",
      "createdAt": "15 minutes"
    }
  ]
}

```

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Sun, 04 Jun 2023 08:13:05 GMT
Content-Type	application/json;charset=UTF-8
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "contractName": "Contract name",
  "contractDescription": "Set a brief description of the contract",
  "contractAddress": "0x2E7D95Fe3843BcDcFac09bf82Dbb793814303032c",
  "contractFunds": 456
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑ ↓	Passed	↑ ↓	Failed	↑ ↓	Skipped	↑ ↓
has contractName		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		2		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.28. IT-49-01, Pricing data greek demo

Iteration: 1 - greek demo

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** POST
- Request URL:** <http://6441d618-4427-4df3-a1fe-7733d5d27110.westeurope.azurecontainer.io/score>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 277ms
- Mean size per request:** 32B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	f9804521-44f2-404d-a5a2-afb987021e84
Host	6441d618-4427-4df3-a1fe-7733d5d27110.westeurope.azurecontainer.io
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	1189

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "Inputs": {
    "data": [
      {
        "temperature_2m (°C)": 5,
        "rain (mm)": 0,
        "snowfall (cm)": 0,
        "windspeed_10m (km/h)": 2,
        "temperature_2m_max (°C)": 15,
        "temperature_2m_min (°C)": 0,
        "communityConsumption": 9542,
        "load": 564287,
        "Brent": 125,
        "time_00": false,
        "time_01": false,
        "time_02": false,
        "time_03": false,
        "time_04": false,
        "time_05": false,
        "time_06": false,
        "time_07": false,
        "time_08": false,
        "time_09": false,
        "time_10": false,
        "time_11": false,
        "time_12": false,
        "time_13": false,
        "time_14": false,
        "time_15": false,
        "time_16": false,
        "time_17": false,
        "time_18": false,
        "time_19": false,
        "time_20": false,
        "time_21": false,
        "time_22": false,
        "time_23": false
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	32
Content-Type	application/json
Date	Mon, 05 Jun 2023 09:28:56 GMT
Server	nginx
X-Ms-Client-Request-Id	909b0ba2-35e5-4de9-b4f2-04ead0f1363c

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

X-Ms-Request-Id	909b0ba2-35e5-4de9-b4f2-04ead0f1363c
X-Ms-Run-Fn-Exec-Ms	113.681
X-Ms-Run-Function-Failed	False
X-Ms-Server-Version	azmlnfsrv/0.8.3
X-Request-Id	b8c1c27c-a530-4f91-9a12-5d43f4650930

RESPONSE BODY

```
{
  "Results": [
    161.1930244189823
  ]
}
```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
test results	1	0	0
Total	2	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.29. IT-49-02, pricing data Spanish

Iteration: 1 - spanish demo

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** POST
- Request URL:** <http://b9a34ac0-36aa-4d15-9c4f-f380ed41aa1d.westeurope.azurecontainer.io/score>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 372ms
- Mean size per request:** 33B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	25d38d0e-6599-40b0-afdd-7a82e0dd0b73
Host	b9a34ac0-36aa-4d15-9c4f-f380ed41aa1d.westeurope.azurecontainer.io
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	1189

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "Inputs": {
    "data": [
      {
        "temperature_2m (°C)": 5,
        "rain (mm)": 0,
        "snowfall (cm)": 0,
        "windspeed_10m (km/h)": 2,
        "temperature_2m_max (°C)": 15,
        "temperature_2m_min (°C)": 0,
        "communityConsumption": 9542,
        "load": 664287,
        "Brent": 125,
        "time_00": false,
        "time_01": false,
        "time_02": false,
        "time_03": false
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	33
Content-Type	application/json
Date	Mon, 05 Jun 2023 09:28:57 GMT
Server	nginx
X-Ms-Client-Request-Id	900fe4d0-7b38-4a37-a3dd-b3427a501193

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

X-Ms-Request-Id	900fe4d0-7b38-4a37-a3dd-b3427a501193
X-Ms-Run-Fn-Exec-Ms	246.392
X-Ms-Run-Function-Failed	False
X-Ms-Server-Version	azmlinfsrv/0.8.3
X-Request-Id	fc77a860-abdc-4a8e-b4ba-696c933bba86

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "Results": [
    149.88084411621094
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
test results		1		0		0	
Total		2		0		0	

Go

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.30. IT-412-01, Token creation

Iteration: 1 - token

REQUEST INFORMATION

- i Request Method: POST
- i Request URL: <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/token>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- i Response Code: 200 - OK
- i Mean time per request: 219ms
- i Mean size per request: 278B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	c7460010-ebd2-4ea2-aebc-65a131b00b44
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	59

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "username": "devC1rce",
  "password": "J1NT8qeGbu3hokPQ7hrs"
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	278
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "access_token": [REDACTED]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.31. IT-412-02, Explicit demand response

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 38ms
- Mean size per request:** 1.56KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	b84e906f-45af-4ba5-a07e-70a7baff8150
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1611
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "default",
  "drEventType": "explicit",
  "startDate": "2022-10-24 08:51:37",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": -9576.471000000005
    },
    {
      "value": -9576.471000000005
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓ Passed	↑↓ Failed	↑↓ Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.32. IT-412-03, Explicit demand response with date parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit date

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 37ms
- Mean size per request:** 1.54KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE
100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	e4a3b43c-e799-43ad-b692-4a68a2511969
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1581
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "default",
  "drEventType": "explicit",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": -9576.471000000005
    },
    {
      "value": -2733.3333333333335
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓ Passed	↑↓ Failed	↑↓ Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.33. IT-412-04, Explicit demand response with date parameter, scenario parameter and real time parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit date, scenario and real time (true) ▼

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00&realtime=1&scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 33ms
- Mean size per request:** 284B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	6da5d26d-1f0a-4957-b4b7-6c277a5827ac
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	283
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "sc0101",
  "drEventType": "explicit realtime",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 15,
  "durationType": "minute",
  "interval": 15,
  "interval_type": "minute",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": 0
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.34. IT-412-05, Explicit demand response with scenario parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit scenario

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 35ms
- Mean size per request:** 1.62KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	31157690-67d4-4082-9a16-8fbcdfb38102
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1668
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "sc0101",
  "drEventType": "explicit",
  "startDate": "2022-10-24 08:51:37",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": 6557.8599999999996
    },
    {
      "value": 737.9192499999999
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.35. IT-412-06, Explicit demand response with real time parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit real time (true)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?realtime=1>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 34ms
- Mean size per request:** 284B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	42e4922c-c3fd-4cfa-a9f4-ba038195f136
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	284
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "default",
  "drEventType": "explicit realtime",
  "startDate": "2022-10-24 08:51:37",
  "duration": 15,
  "durationType": "minute",
  "interval": 15,
  "interval_type": "minute",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": 0
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	T1	Passed	T1	Failed	T1	Skipped	T1
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.36. IT-412-07, Explicit demand response with date parameter and real time parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit date and real time (true) ✓

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00&realtime=1&scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 35ms
- Mean size per request:** 283B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	efc03cf-2a07-4d2b-b226-e4f4e4521d75
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	283
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "sc0101",
  "drEventType": "explicit_realtime",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 15,
  "durationType": "minute",
  "interval": 15,
  "interval_type": "minute",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": 0
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑	Passed	↓	Failed	↑	Skipped	↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.37. IT-412-08, Explicit demand response with date parameter and scenario parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit date and scenario

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00&scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 36ms
- Mean size per request:** 1.62KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	421f1b74-84d2-44ca-afab-3223ad920b33
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1659
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "sc0101",
  "drEventType": "explicit",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": 1167.273999999995
    },
    {
      "value": 1167.273999999995
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.38. IT-412-09, Explicit demand response with scenario parameter and real time parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit scenario and real time (true)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00&realtime=1&scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 38ms
- Mean size per request:** 283B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	efc03cf-2a07-4d2b-b226-e4f4e4521d75
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	283
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "sc0101",
  "drEventType": "explicit realtime",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 15,
  "durationType": "minute",
  "interval": 15,
  "interval_type": "minute",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": 0
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	T1	Passed	T1	Failed	T1	Skipped	T1
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.39. IT-412-10, Implicit demand response

Iteration: 1 - DR implicit

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drimplicit>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 70ms
- Mean size per request:** 4.72KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	e54eb176-9127-4160-802e-6b7d8b05fa63
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	5052
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "default",
  "drEventType": "implicit",
  "startDate": "2022-10-24 00:51:37",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "absolute",
  "signalUnit": "euro",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": 101.94061199999999
    },
    {
      "value": 100.504744
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.40. IT-412-11, Implicit demand response with date parameter and scenario parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR implicit date and scenario

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drimPLICIT?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00&scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 70ms
- Mean size per request:** 4.72KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	93cfb536-da15-4098-aa30-01221202cc8d
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:38 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	4829
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "sce101",
  "drEventType": "implicit",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "absolute",
  "signalUnit": "euro",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": 185.25
    },
    {
      "value": 184.24
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.41. IT-412-12, Implicit demand response with date parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR implicit date

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drimplicit?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 70ms
- Mean size per request:** 4.73KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	da858174-e953-4d14-a06e-863e0d49818d
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:38 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	4841
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "default",
  "drEventType": "implicit",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "absolute",
  "signalUnit": "euro",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": 241.75
    },
    {
      "value": 211.876
    }
  ]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.42. IT-412-13, Implicit demand response with scenario parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR implicit scenario

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drimplicit?scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 68ms
- Mean size per request:** 4.72KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	60c5da96-4efe-4b05-8c0c-c27bcf81c4d0
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:38 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	5067
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.43. IT-412-14, Token creation

Iteration: 1 - Create token

REQUEST INFORMATION

- ❗ Request Method: POST
- ❗ Request URL: https://accept.fcirce.es/market/create_token

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- ❗ Response Code: 200 - OK
- ⌚ Mean time per request: 219ms
- 📏 Mean size per request: 2768

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	57d046b6-967f-4708-bbb9-d068f82046a1
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	69

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "username": "training",
  "password": "Arqch[0r&+?^2k]8"
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:40:28 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	276
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "access_token": [REDACTED]
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.44. IT-412-15, Energy prices retrieval for a specific date

Iteration: 1 - Get_data

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method: **GET**
- Request URL: <https://accept.fcirce.es/market/pricing>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code: **200 - OK**
- Mean time per request: **68ms**
- Mean size per request: **1.01KB**

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	1f06063d-b592-417a-97b8-7fecc00bad90
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	49

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "year": 2022,
  "month": 6,
  "day": 8,
  "hour": 13
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:40:29 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1032
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "data": {
    "2022-10-24 10:00:00": 88.507195,
    "2022-10-24 11:00:00": 85.81104,
    "2022-10-24 12:00:00": 79.48544,
    "2022-10-24 13:00:00": 74.041725,
    "2022-10-24 14:00:00": 58.94369,
    "2022-10-24 15:00:00": 53.660236,
    "2022-10-24 16:00:00": 54.07508,
    "2022-10-24 17:00:00": 77.7997,
    "2022-10-24 18:00:00": 85.224625,
    "2022-10-24 19:00:00": 106.338844,
    "2022-10-24 20:00:00": 128.02188,
    "2022-10-24 21:00:00": 121.67363,
    "2022-10-24 22:00:00": 111.38073,
    "2022-10-24 23:00:00": 99.335075,
    "2022-10-24 00:00:00": 87.71775
  }
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
contains data		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		2		0		0	

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.45. IT-412-16, Energy prices retrieval for today's date

Iteration: 1 - Get_data (empty json body)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- 📌 Request Method: GET
- 📌 Request URL: <https://accept.fcirce.es/market/pricing>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- 📌 Response Code: 200 - OK
- 📌 Mean time per request: 67ms
- 📌 Mean size per request: 1.01KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	4a5d3ab0-e6eb-4b10-a63f-f4ecc1b1f5e8
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	2

REQUEST BODY

{}
Copy to Clipboard

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:40:29 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1032
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "data": {
    "2022-10-24 10:00:00": 88.507195,
    "2022-10-24 11:00:00": 85.81184,
    "2022-10-24 12:00:00": 79.40544,
    "2022-10-24 13:00:00": 74.841723,
    "2022-10-24 14:00:00": 58.94369,
    "2022-10-24 15:00:00": 53.668236,
    "2022-10-24 16:00:00": 54.87588,
    "2022-10-24 17:00:00": 77.7997,
    "2022-10-24 18:00:00": 85.224625,
    "2022-10-24 19:00:00": 100.338844,
    "2022-10-24 20:00:00": 128.82188,
    "2022-10-24 21:00:00": 121.67363,
    "2022-10-24 22:00:00": 111.38875,
    "2022-10-24 23:00:00": 98.338075,
  }
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
contains data	1	0	0
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	2	0	0

9.2.46. IT-412-17, Store DR result

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

Iteration: 1 - store result

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method: **POST**
- Request URL: <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/dresult>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code: **200 - OK**
- Mean time per request: **53ms**
- Mean size per request: **44B**

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json

Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	88f5b442-fea7-4007-afb6-67068db58311
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	44
Cookie	cookiesession1=678A3E1349E373FCEAF89B5FEFC83F51

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "req_id": "1",
  "status": "done"
}

```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

9.2.47. IT-412-18, Get DR result

Iteration: 1 - get result

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/dresult?req_id=1

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 53ms
- Mean size per request:** 44B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	Bearer
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	69117ce0-a9f9-4e12-85ac-a9d29a2ef917
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Cookie	cookiesession1=678A3E1349E373FCEAF89B5FEFC83F51

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Thu, 22 Jun 2023 18:40:08 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	44
Connection	keep-alive

D6.3 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v2

RESPONSE BODY

```
{
  "req_id": "1",
  "status": "done"
}
```

Copy to Clipboard

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	